

UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST OF ENGLAND, BRISTOL

MASTER OF SCIENCE IN MARKETING COMMUNICATION

DEPARTMENT OF BRISTOL BUSINESS SCHOOL

Understanding the important factors influencing customers' online purchasing decisions in the fashion clothing for Gen Z consumers of Darjeeling Pulbazar in the district of Darjeeling, West Bengal, India.

Submitted by

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A Dissertation submitted as a requirement for the award of Master of Science in Marketing Communication.

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Declaration

At the University of West England in Bristol, this study was completed for the Master of Science in Marketing Communication degree. The report is entirely original to me and hasn't been submitted anywhere else. When someone else's work is referenced or used, it is properly credited.

Abstract

Purpose: The purpose of this study is to understand the important factors influencing customers' online purchasing decisions in the fashion clothing for Gen Z consumers.

This study was done to better understand Gen Z consumers' attitudes toward online shopping, to comprehend which brand-related factors have an impact on consumers' choices when they purchase online, whether Gen Z customers prefer to shop online or in-store, and most crucially, which aspects of the digital marketing mix influence consumers' choices the most.

Methodology: For this study, a quantitative methodology was used to conduct an online survey who commonly make purchases online in India. All of the data will be gathered by Qualtrics utilising an online survey. The URL and QR code for the survey will be provided to respondents. A Likert scale has been used to measure progress. When data collection is complete, SPSS software will be used to analyse the data.

Findings: Product genuity, product quality, and the availability of a free return policy are some of the most crucial considerations when making an online purchase decision. Customer reviews are also crucial, and if a brand is well-known, customers are more likely to feel confident making a purchase.

Recommendations: Still believe that any online e-commerce platform should prioritise "ease of use" of an app when considering how to best market its goods. Second, most e-commerce platforms should have a free return policy accessible, or at least a little cost for returning the item. Additionally, in order to reach a broad audience, brand awareness is crucial.

Limitations: The major obstacles to this research's ability to gather the data were a lack of time and respondents.

Keywords: fashion clothing, purchasing decision, digital marketing mix, darjeeling, gen z, eCommerce

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Chapter One

Introduction

This research is conducted to understand how online purchasing behaviour and what factors in the Digital Marketing Mix have impacted the Darjeeling Gen Z consumer in particular. And how they are shifting from conventional in-store purchases to online purchasing.

In recent years, marketing has adopted innovative methods to attract and retain a diverse range of customers to purchase their products and services. The use of digital media by marketers to advertise their products and services via internet-based promotional activities is known as digital marketing. Businesses may now employ digital marketing to increase brand awareness, grow their client base, and get a higher ROI. It enables advertisers to interact with customers directly 24 hours a day, seven days a week. It also assists large, medium, and small businesses in more successfully marketing their products and maintaining direct touch with their consumers. It aids in the digital marketing of products to millions of consumers at the same time. It influences client purchase decisions. It also aids in the development of a favourable brand image. It costs less than typical marketing methods. As a result, it has proved to be an outstanding ecommerce companion. (M & B, 2019)

Ramesh M. and Vidhya B., did a similar study in Vellore City, Tamil Nadu, India, *to find out the effect of digital marketing on online consumer buying behavior*. Where in findings from descriptive statistics, it is clearly learnt that the consumers have average opinion on digital marketing and its effectiveness have minimal online buying behavior. Based on the chi-square test, it is understood that there is a significant association between consumers' socio-economic factors, their perception of digital marketing and their online buying behavior. The multiple regression analysis has proven that 92% of 75 Ramesh, Vidhya Journal of Services Research, Volume 19, Number 2 (October 2019 - March 2020) consumers online buying behavior is affected by their perception on digital marketing and its effectiveness. Based on Kendall's W Test, it is found that content marketing is the highly preferable digital marketing channel to take online buying decisions by consumers. (Vedatya Institute, 2019)

There has been conducted a similar study on customer *satisfaction towards online shopping in Darjeeling, West Bengal*. Where Aju Kurian investigated the factors that influence customer's online shopping decisions and how these factors, like, (which customers favour online shopping, features that customers expect at an online shopping portal, different payment and delivery systems preferred by the customers, inhibitions faced by customers during online purchases, how these factors, interact to influence customer purchase decisions) affect customer satisfaction, and the findings and results reflect the perceptions, preferences, and factors influencing satisfaction of online shoppers in Siliguri. Although the Siliguri region was highlighted in this research paper rather than merely Darjeeling, this work may not precisely encompass understanding the purchasing behaviour of customers in Darjeeling particularly. (Kurian, 2018).

Hence, this research has been focused primarily on Darjeeling customers' perspective on their online purchasing decisions.

1.1 Scope of the study

This research examines customers' perceptions of the following online purchasing elements and how their presence or absence in an online shopping environment affects customer satisfaction; What online purchase platforms do customers prefer? What is the average number of fashion apparel goods that buyers like to buy online? What sorts of delivery services do customers prefer: cash on delivery, online payments, a free return policy, or product tracking? Also, which aspects of the app's user experience do they favour, such as ease of use, product variety presentation, feedback from other customers, or offers and promotions? Finally, what effect does brand image have on customer purchasing decisions?

1.2 Definitions

1.2.1 Gen Z

Generation Z according to "Generate Z -Affiliate Marketing Product Review Site" (2021), is a more educated, well-behaved, stressed, and depressed generation than prior Generation. Generation Z, or Gen Z for short, is a generation of individuals born between the mid -1990s and the early 2010s (Generation Z - Affiliate Marketing Product Review Site", 2021)

1.2.2 Darjeeling:

Darjeeling is a northern district of West Bengal state in eastern India and famous for its beautiful Himalayas hill station & and Darjeeling tea and has been crowned with the honour of being the queen of all hill stations in the nation. (Darjeeling District Information-Sensonmedia, n.d.)

Geographically, the district is separated into two sections: the hills and the plains. Darjeeling Gorkha Autonomous Hill Council, an independent administrative body under the West Bengal state government, governs the whole mountainous portion of the district. Darjeeling, Kurseong, and Kalimpong are the three hill subdivisions covered by the council. The Darjeeling Himalayan foothills are part of the Siliguri subdivision and are also known as Terrain. Siliguri is located at the foot of the hills and is flanked on the north by the Himalayas, on the south by Bihar state's Purnia district, on the east by Jalpaiguri district, and on the west by Nepal. (Darjeeling District , West Bengal, n.d.)

Darjeeling is divided into four sub-districts: Darjeeling (Sadar), Kurseong, Siliguri, and Mirik. The following are the sub-divisional distributions of C.D blocks and Urban Municipalities: (Census Department | Darjeeling District, Government of West Bengal | India, n.d.)

1. Darjeeling Sadar Sub-Division includes Darjeeling Pulbazar, RangliRangliot, and JorebunglowSukhiapokhari C.D Blocks, as well as Darjeeling Municipality.
2. Kurseong Sub-Division is made up of Kurseong C.D Blocks and the Kurseong Municipality.
3. Siliguri Sub-Division includes the C.D Blocks of Matigara, Naxalbari, Phansidewa, and Kharibari, as well as the Siliguri Municipal Corporation.
4. Mirik Sub-Division is made up of Mirik C and D Blocks, as well as Mirik Municipality.

1.2.3 eCommerce:

The eCommerce market segment Fashion includes the commercial (B2C) sale of apparel (for men, women, and children), footwear (e.g., leather shoes, sneakers, luxury footwear, as well as textile and other footwear), luggage and bags (e.g., suitcases, purses, and briefcases), and accessories (e.g., hats and caps, watches and jewellery) through a digital channel." Internet shops (e.g., amazon.com) and online fashion stores (e.g., Asos, Zalando, Nordstrom) are the primary sales channels in this market sector (e.g., eBags, zara.com, clarks.com, samsonite.com). This sector excludes dedicated outdoor and sports apparel, outdoor and sports footwear, and infant garments (see: Toys, Hobby & DIY). This market group also excludes the buying and resale of secondhand fashion items. All monetary numbers are based on annual gross income and do not include shipping expenses.". (Statista, 2022)

1.2.4 eCommerce in India:

The majority of the leading eCommerce firms are present in India and are playing significant roles in capturing Indian markets. Amazon India, Flipkart, Myntra, Paytm, SnapDeal, AJIO, Alibaba Group, ShopClues, Paytm Mall, Tata Cliq, and other online retailers such as IndiaMART, FirstCry, Nykaa, BookMyShow, EBay, Rediff, MakeMyTrip, LimeRoad, Bigbasket, Jabong, Homeshop18, and others are important influencing factors that provide comfort, convenience, choice These considerations paved the path for such marketers to enter the digital marketing sector. (Haque & Alam, 2021)

The increasing purchasing power of Indian customers is driving the growth of internet shopping in India. According to TheGlobalStatistics, the majority of Indians utilise social media sites such as Instagram, Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Pinterest, MX TakaTak, Moj, and Skype to build their network and socialise with people from all over the world. (*India Social Media Statistics 2022 | Most Used Top Platforms, 2022*)

E-commerce has continued to expand quickly all around the world. According to reports from February 2019, 57% of the world's population was online, with a growth rate of 13% between 2014 and 2018. (Lamb, 2019).

India, one of the most populous countries in Asia, is expected to triple its total consumption from US\$1.3 trillion in 2016 to US\$3.6 trillion in 2027, with a sizable portion of that amount expected to be spent online thanks to the country's robust IT infrastructure that has been developed over time (E-commerce in India: Industry Overview, Market Size & Growth| IBEF, 2018). e-increased

commerce's efficiency and customer comfort allow consumers to spend less time searching for products, resulting in lower total aggregated prices for a variety of commodities as compared to offline counterparts (Kumar & Sadarangani, 2018; Nagar & Gandotra, 2016). This may be the cause of the frequent observation of price concern in internet shoppers (Vijayasathy & Jones, 2000).

E-commerce has sparked a new revolution that is altering how companies purchase and dispense goods and services. New approaches have developed. Geographical distances play a smaller influence in developing business partnerships. E-commerce is the way of the future of retail. The internet industry will continue to expand strongly as 3G and 4G wireless communication technologies are deployed. India will have 30 to 70 million internet users in 3 to 5 years, which is equal to, if not more than, many developed nations. The Indian internet economy will then have greater significance. E-commerce is now a household term in Indian culture and is ingrained in every aspect of our everyday lives. Mitra, A. (2013).

1.2.5 Amazon India:

Jeff Bezos founded Amazon in 1994 as the first major firm to sell goods and services via the internet. Amazon began as an online book store and quickly evolved to include DVDs, video games, electronics, clothes, and other items, to the point where the company logo depicts that they provide everything from A to Z. (History.com Editors, 2022)

Amazon takes every attempt to earn the confidence and loyalty of its customers. They provide state shipping and have retail locations in various countries. It also purchases client data and information in order to suit consumer expectations and aspirations. Amazon: What We Do (Amazon, 2022). Amazon was one of the first firms in the world to sell things online, and it competes with Flipkart, Myntra, Ebay, Ajo, and SnapDeal. (Haque & Alam, 2021)

According to (Statista, 2022) Amazon.in is leading the Indian e-commerce market, with e-commerce net sales of US\$ 1,082 million in 2020 generated in India, followed by Ajo.com with US\$ 983 million [S.J25].

1.3 Research questions:

- **Research question 1**

What are the main factors in the Digital marketing mix that influence customers' online fashion clothing purchasing decisions in the Darjeeling district of India?

- **Research question 2**

What are the most important factors in the digital marketing mix that influence customers while purchasing online?

1. Which of the following factors in user experience is the most important to prioritise: ease of use, product variety display, reviews, and promotions & sales?
2. Which platform do customers prefer for purchasing online?
3. What is the average amount of the products in fashion clothing that customers like to purchase online?
4. Which type of delivery service do customers prefer: cash on delivery, online payments, free return policy, or tracking?

- **Research question 3**

What factors of a brand influence customers in purchasing online?

1. What impact does brand image have on customer purchasing decisions?
2. Does quality matter over brand and vice versa?

- **Research question 4**

Which do you prefer: online shopping or in-store shopping?

1. Is online shopping more popular than in-store shopping?
2. Which platforms of shopping do customers rely on the most?

1.4 Aim:

This research aims to identify and evaluate the most important factors in the Digital Marketing Mix in online purchasing decisions in the Fashion Clothes affecting Gen Z consumers in Darjeeling Pulbazar in the district of Darjeeling, West Bengal, India.

1.5 Objectives:

- Is to understand what factors in the Digital Marketing Mix is more important for Gen Z in online purchasing
- Is to understand the perspective of Gen Z consumers towards online purchasing.
- Is to understand what factors in brand influence in making decisions in online purchasing
- Is to understand whether Gen Z customers prefer to shop online or in-store

Chapter Two

Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

This chapter gives a comprehensive description of the approaches used in Darjeeling's Gen Z customers' fast fashion garment purchasing decisions. This chapter also discusses the Digital Marketing Mix, E-marketing, Gen Z, Purchase Decision-Making style of Gen Z, Brand influence, Fashion Apparel, Locations (both online and offline retailers), and Purchasing Decision.

2.2 Digital Marketing mix

According to (Silverman, 1995) A Marketing Mix the Historical Context and Development of the Marketing Mix, Butler defined marketing in 1911 as "everything the promoter of a product has to accomplish prior to his real use of salesmen and advertising." The agencies of demand formation were thus characterised by Shaw (1916) as "middlemen" (i.e., wholesalers), "direct salesmen," and "advertising." and also defined demand creation organisation as "market analysis" (i.e., market research) and "pricing policies." Converse then precisely described the essential elements of marketing in a corporation in 1930. (Product, price, distribution, advertising and selling). As per Cullition (1948), the function of marketing administrator is a "combination of components." Communications, channels, product performance, pricing, and other "order-getting components" have been specified. Borden (1953) applied the term marketing mix to product planning, pricing, branding, distribution channels, personal selling, advertising, promotion, packaging, display, servicing, physical handling, and fact finding) and programme forces (consumer attitudes and methods, competition, and government controls.). By 1960, McCarthy had standardised the concept of the marketing mix as the Four P's: Product, Place, Price, and Promotion. Based on the work of Frey (1956) and Kelly and Lazer (1958), "The" marketing mix was created.

A marketing mixes. It is a tool or group of factors that a business can control in order to persuade customers to buy its products. Jerome McCarthy created the marketing mix, also known as the 4 Ps of Product, Price, Place, and Promotion, in 1960, and it is still used by many marketers as an essential part of creating and implementing marketing strategy. People, Process, and Physical Evidence are three new factors that have been added to the 4 Ps to better represent service delivery. (Chaffey & Ellis-Chadwick, 2012)

It is a catch-all phrase for the promotion of goods or services through the use of digital technology, namely the Internet, mobile devices, display advertising, and other digital media. The way companies and businesses use technology and digital marketing has changed as a result of how digital marketing has evolved since the 1990s and 2000s. As digital platforms are being incorporated into marketing strategies and as more individuals use digital devices instead of visiting physical stores, digital marketing efforts are becoming more common. Because digital

marketing depends on rapidly expanding technology, the same characteristics should be anticipated from new innovations in digital marketing. (Sudha, M., & Sheena, K. ,2017, September)

Study by (Arora & Aggarwal, 2018) shows that among Indian women, the benefits of price, convenience, and product diversity have a strong favourable impact on their attitudes toward online shopping. There is also a large positive correlation between their attitudes and their intention to shop online. The most significant benefit that Indian women saw as being beneficial was product diversity.

As stated by (Devi, E. B.) The essential need for digital marketing in everyone's life is created by Covid-19. Customers are willing to invest a significant amount of their free time in researching digital marketing and advertising. Businesses must rely on digital technologies; among the widely utilised ones are google.com, facebook.com, youtube.com, amazon.com, flipkart.com, meesho, etc. These days, both public and private enterprises must provide their clients digital platforms.

This study appears to have contributed to the understanding that the Digital Marketing Mix aids in finding the benefits that any business or product can provide to customers, and helps create a profitable product offering, aids in the planning, organisation, and execution of successful marketing initiatives. helps organisations avoid wasteful costs and make the most of their advantages. Moreover, as a result of the development of digital marketing, how organisations and enterprises use technology has changed. Finally, the most crucial factors are pricing, shopping convenience, product diversity, and availability, particularly for Indian women.

2.3 4Ps of Marketing Mix:

1. **Product:**

According to (Constantinides, 2006) The term "product" refers to all of the components and aspects required to provide a service that adds value to the customer. Products might vary in various ways depending on the needs of the customers. Some needed electrical products or domestic objects, from tiny to large, every need and occasionally unusual thing can be classified as a product. However, this study is limited to Fashion Apparel from the fast fashion business. Another significant study found that customers' perceptions of the website's product diversity and their shopping pleasure both increased when the products were organised into more subcategories in the selection menu. This resulted in an improvement in their views toward the online store. (Chang, 2011) (Shah Alam & Mohd Yasin, 2010) found five criteria that have a strong association with online purchasing satisfaction: website design, dependability, product diversity, and delivery performance. Furthermore, (Mallapragada et al., 2016) found that online stores with a wide range of product categories tend to benefit online shoppers more. Consumers' intentions to buy are positively impacted by product quality. The packaging of the goods is a significant component that could potentially influence consumer purchasing intention in addition to the product quality. (Mirabi, 2015). (Farahani et al., 2021) demonstrated how

packaging's aesthetic and practical effects affected consumers' decisions to buy food. The only component of the marketing mix that a firm can adjust to suit its needs is its product, which also happens to be its biggest source of money. (Anjelika, F..., & Sinaga, T. M... 2022)

2. Price:

The price is the amount of money that a customer is willing to pay for a product or service. And according to (Davies & Brush, 1997) Price and other costs of the service sector demonstrate the management of various costs borne by customers in obtaining the benefits from generating the services. In consumer cooperatives, the first and most important objective is to satisfy consumers, which should be factored into pricing, followed by making a profit, increasing sales, gaining market share, and ensuring the company's existence and expansion. (M. H. Mostaani, 2005). According to Biswas, A., & Blair, E. A. (1991) Price reduction may influence consumers' perceptions of prices and ultimately their purchase intentions. (Brynjolfsson & Smith, 2000) showed that pricing for goods and services online are between 8 and 15 percent less expensive than those for comparable goods in conventional retail stores. The lack of direct costs associated with supplying the goods is most likely the cause of the cheaper price (e.g. no rental cost, centralised inventory, etc.). (Reibstein, 2002) also found in his research that, on average, online shoppers believe and act as though pricing is the most important factor in luring them to an e-commerce website. In the context of online buying, researchers in the Indian market identified three buyer segments: value singularity, quality at any price, and reputation/recreation (Gehrt et al., 2012). Therefore, for a specific customer group, price is not their top priority while shopping online. E-commerce can occasionally be a profitable choice for customers due to unique deals made by online suppliers as well as price reductions. The "buy one, get one free" promotion, free admission to an event, a discount certificate good for future purchases, free presents for every nth client, festival exchange offers, etc. are examples of special offers. (Arora & Aggarwal, 2018b).

3. Place:

Place refers to administrative decisions about where customers should receive services, which may include electronic/physical distribution routes (Davies & Brush, 1997) Consumer cooperatives are a type of distribution channel that can develop a relationship between consumers and manufacturers while also playing an important role in lowering prices and reducing the growth of unnecessary dealers. (M. H. Mostaani, 2005). Place also affects customer interest when it comes to making a purchasing decision. Place is a marketing strategy that adds value by educating and stimulating demand for promoted goods by persuading customers to purchase the goods on offer. In general, a place has five success indicators,

including coupons, product samples, discounts, lucky draws, and purchasing competitions. (Anjelika, F. . . , & Sinaga, T. M. . . 2022). Kurniawan, A. R. (2018) asserts that location is where business owners choose the site of their enterprise and that this decision is the most crucial aspect of operating a business. Additionally, there are a number of factors to take into account when selecting a strategic site to launch a business, including conducting market research, trading areas, access roads, competition, and cleanliness.

4. Promotion:

Marketing communication is evolving and changing as new tools, theories, methods, technology advancements, and cultural variables all combine to have an impact on how marketers communicate their message to the targeted audience. Symbolic consumption in a marketing campaign is likely to encourage customers to buy a product or service that will reinforce their identities. Sales promotion activities have increased significantly online as e-commerce has grown. Coupons, discounts, free or low-cost gifts, contests, banner ads, and sponsored links are examples of sales promotion tools. Because online promotion is addressed to consumers, the impact of the sales campaign can be easily monitored depending on the level of interaction on the website. (Abdul Lasi & Mohamed Salim, 2020). Promotion is one of the strategies used to attract customers' attention. It takes the form of a combination of the store's physical attributes, which are broken down into four categories: the exterior, the general interior, the store layout, and the interior display, which includes the store's architecture, layout, lighting, display, colour, and aroma. (Anjelika, F..., & Sinaga, T. M... 2022).

2.4 E-marketing:

E-marketing is frequently regarded as an inherent part of a business's entire marketing strategy, which means that overall marketing strategy objectives can be accommodated to it. Objectives with a restricted scope are assigned to internet marketing. The internet, a new type of communication, comprises a wide and extensive network that serves various internet users/consumers. Both consumers and advertising suppliers may have a part in the online information provider in this scenario. Users can construct websites, write articles on them, and advertise various products. (Abdul Lasi & Mohamed Salim, 2020). Since consumers progressively become more resistant to certain marketing impacts over time, the more innovative and cutting-edge an approach, the more effectively it spreads throughout its environment. A careful and simple integration of advertisements into a specific target group's interest groups should be the goal of marketing. Consequently, there are numerous trends in marketing communication. If a certain trend is successful, mainstream organisations will eventually adopt it. Because of these developments, businesses are working hard to stay current, continually attract new customers, and keep their existing clientele. Marketing initiatives must therefore match the established communication goals. This could take the form of

developing brand loyalty, influencing consumer sentiments, or improving product awareness. (Lukach, B., & Kostiuk, Y. 2022).

2.5 Gen Z

Generation Z according to "Generate Z -Affiliate Marketing Product Review Site" (2021), is a more educated, well-behaved, stressed, and depressed generation than prior Generation. Generation Z, or Gen Z for short, is a generation of individuals born between the mid -1990s and the early 2010s (Generation Z - Affiliate Marketing Product Review Site", 2021) Early candidates included Generation Z, the iGeneration, and Homelanders. (We used the term "post-Millennials" as a placeholder in our first in-depth look at this group.) However, in the last year, Gen Z has made inroads into popular culture and media.Sources ranging from Merriam-Webster and Oxford to the Urban Dictionary now contain this name for the generation that comes after the Millennials, and Google Trends data suggest that "Generation Z" is exceeding other names in people's information searches. While there is no scientific method for determining when a name has stuck, the tide obviously favours Generation Z.

Money is a huge concern for Generation Z. Though this generation is known for its need for rapid gratification, it doesn't seem to extend in buying; similar to Gen Y, Gen Z is satisfied to put off a purchase in order to take the time to do some research. They research online for the greatest prices, read reviews, and test the goods out physically or electronically. (Sladek, S., & Grabinger, A, 2014). And also, XYZ University Survey revealed that despite their early age, 34% of Gen Z is interacting online with friends in other states and 13% is connecting with friends in other countries. Gen Z uses social media to communicate with individuals all over the world. These cultural linkages have proven to be highly potent. Friends can, on a small scale, use their networks to share movies, images, and messages to inform big audiences about global events, whether they be positive or negative. Youth have banded together to address global concerns as a result of this connectedness on a larger scale. (Sladek, S., & Grabinger, A, 2014).

Due to the ongoing political, cultural, and socioeconomic changes that take place in society as a whole, today's young generation's shopping habits tend to differ significantly from those of previous generations. Knowing the consuming traits of Gen Z is crucial since they differ from past generations in terms of consumer values, interests, and beliefs. (Thangavel et al., 2019) It is expected that research into Gen Z's shopping preferences on an e-commerce platform will have new implications for practitioners and add to the body of research already available.

2.5.1 Purchase Decision-Making Style

In their 1993 study, Shim and Kotsiopoulos identified three distinct shopping styles among female fashion consumers: "very involved apparel shoppers," "apathetic apparel shoppers," and "convenience-oriented catalogue shoppers." According to Sinha's 2003 study of Indian customers, there are two distinct purchasing habits: "the fun shoppers" and "the job shoppers." Additionally, Bakewell and Mitchell (2003) examined how Gen Y female shoppers made decisions about their purchases and identified five distinct consumer groups: "recreational

quality seekers," "recreational discount seekers," "trendsetting loyals," "shopping and fashion uninterested," and "confused time/money conserving." According to Loureiro and Breazeale's (2016) research on Generation Y's online apparel purchases, "in-home buying inclination," "convenience consciousness," and "impulse purchase" are the three most significant elements that influence consumers' Internet purchasing orientation.

The opportunity to compare competing products and reviews from customers who have purchased and utilised the item are considered to be the most crucial online buying features for Gen Z. (Van den Bergh & Pallini, 2018).

2.6 Brand Influence

Customers' tendency to continuously choose one brand over rivals for goods and services is known as "brand loyalty." Evidence exists to support the idea that brand loyalty is less important to Gen Z customers. Virtually no young customer purchases a product solely based on the brand name due to the ease with which information (reviews, product comparisons, etc.) can now be accessed online. (Thangavel et al., 2019b) Furthermore, packaging has a significant impact on brand loyalty, which is directly related to customer purchase intent, according to Khraim. (Farahani et al., 2021b). Brand image is a consumer's view of a company based on their memories of a product and how they feel about the company. The following features of a brand can be used to measure brand image: (Prasetyo et al., 2022)

1. Recognizable brands
2. Brands are simply to identify
3. A reputable brand

Individuals engage in problem-solving activities known as purchasing decisions when choosing among two or more behavioural alternatives that are appropriate for a given situation. After going through the stages of the decision-making process, this choice is then deemed to be the most appropriate action in the context of purchasing. Therefore, there are various factors that a customer must consider before making a purchasing decision, including: (Prasetyo et al., 2022)

1. Problem Recognition (Problem Recognition)
2. Information Search (Information Search)
3. Alternative Evaluation
4. Purchase Decision (Purchase Decision)
5. Post-Purchase Behavior

Every product that is marketed on the market undoubtedly has a brand, which sets one thing apart from another. A brand is a name, symbol, sign, design, or mix of these things that is used to represent an individual, group, or business in goods and services in order to set it apart from competing services and products. (2020)

A brand has been considered as basically being a seller's commitment to continuously provide buyers with a certain set of features, perks, and services (Kotler, P.2000)

The problem is to create a powerful brand image for the brand, which means that the brand is more than just a name. The most prosperous companies have built riches through client acquisition and retention as a result of fusing an efficient product, distinctive character, and added values in the eyes of the consumer (Doyle, P., & Stern, P. 2006).

Twelve key themes of brand definitions

Adapted from De Chernatony and Dall'Olmio Riley, (1998)

2.6.1 Fashion Apparel

The fashion apparel market has seen tremendous change, especially in the last 20 years as the industry's borders have begun to widen (Djelic & Ainamo, 1999)

As "the process of social dissemination by which a new style is adopted by some group of customers," fashion is significant to many consumers. Numerous facets of our life are influenced by fashion, which has both economic and social significance and gives people a means of self-expression and identity formation. Therefore, it is crucial to comprehend how decisions are made in the fashion sector.

Human beings have demonstrated an instinctive urge to enhance their outer appearances in front of society from the dawn of human civilisation. People carefully craft nice social impressions through their consuming endeavours because they aspire to receive favourable social assessments (Orehek et al., 2019).

Consumers of women's clothing show greater interest in when compared to male consumers' attractiveness, and this interest in appearance that is specific to gender is positively associated to innovativeness in fashion apparel (Park & Chung, 2013)

2.7 Location

(Salomon & Koppelman, 1988) address the underlying elements influencing the decision between in-store and teleshopping in one of the first comprehensive studies. Shopping,

according to their definition, is the process of gathering data on a product's attributes before making a purchase choice. The perceptions of shopping alternatives (being social, enjoyable, time-efficient, etc.) are thought to be influenced by alternative-specific attributes (service, delivery, travel time, etc.), as well as by personal characteristics (socioeconomic background). Attitudes toward shopping alternatives (enjoying the store or shopping experience, variety seeking, perceptions of risk, service quality, etc. According to research by Farag et al., (2005), young, single males with high incomes and educational levels who reside in urban residential areas have more favourable attitudes regarding internet shopping and engage in it more frequently. For instance, Scarpi et al. (2014) discovered that in-store buying has a stronger association with shopping for enjoyment than online shopping. Another main criterion to shop online often referred to is the (lower) price in combination with facilitated (Farag et al.,2005).

According to research by Schmidt and Axhausen (2019), price advantages are a major reason why Swiss consumers choose to shop online. As a result, respondents who have more favourable attitudes toward online shopping show higher levels of cost sensitivity, which can be attributed to the expanded choice set those results from effectively weighing both purchasing channels.

2.7.1 In-store:

Despite an expanding selection of online shopping options, brick-and-mortar stores continue to be the primary place where customers shop for the majority of their needs. (Cox et al., 2005) Some claim that shoppers go to stores looking for social encounters. The marketplace "has always been a centre of social activity," according to Tauber, (1972). The enjoyment of browsing may differ according to affluence. It was previously thought that looking about or window shopping may substitute for making a purchase. (Cox et al., 2005b). It is even more crucial for merchants to comprehend how they may improve customers' offline shopping experiences in these challenging times. Retailers are utilising "digital retail" as a new type of retail as a response to these difficulties. This type of retail uses information and communication technologies (such as smartphones) to engage customers, increase sales, and provide distinctive shopping experiences that are superior to pure online shopping. (Zimmermann et al., 2022)

2.8 Purchasing decisions

A purchasing decision is the thinking process that takes a consumer from understanding a need to developing possibilities and selecting a specific brand and product. It is the process through which consumers become aware of and define their wants, get information on how to best meet these needs, evaluate various available options, make a purchasing decision, and evaluate their purchase. (Millwood, 2021) And the focus of this research has been on how Generation Z consumers make online purchasing decisions using the factors in the digital marketing mix. Understanding consumer behaviour and the purchasing decision-making process Businesses have better ideas than competitors on how to build effective marketing campaigns that appeal to the target market and provide higher customer value. eCommerce businesses have a special

opportunity to optimise it. Because online customers generate so much more data than those in brick-and-mortar stores, online retailers may utilise that data to apply conversion strategies at every stage of the process. (Millwood, 2021).

On the essential for business, consumers perform as actors. In general, people who buy or use goods and services are referred to as consumers; nevertheless, there is a small distinction between a buyer and a consumer. Buyers are those who are functioning as institutional, industrial, or final buyers. Consumers display a variety of behavioural patterns when making purchases and getting rid of products, services, ideas, or experiences. They are anxiously watching the fashion sectors for indications that would help them form impressions that will satisfy their requirements. Because customers and prospects occasionally experience severe roadblocks in their decision-making process, businesses often run into blockages where the message is not getting through to their customers and prospects. If not, then everyone of them ought to be totally committed, devoted, enthusiastic, and frequent customers, but that is not the case. Today's decision-making is greatly influenced by the availability and clarity of information, therefore it's critical to look at the barriers and fallacies that prevent prospects from becoming customers or existing customers from making repeat purchases. (Sudha, M., & Sheena, K., 2017, September)

Purchasing decisions are thought of as a simple concept of how consumers evaluate product pricing and decide if it is worth affording. Purchasing decisions, on the other hand, give wider study-worthy concerns that are not restricted to product price perception. An individual was limited in how much knowledge he or she possessed, including product pricing knowledge. As a result, there is a tendency to prioritise the need for satisfying fulfilment over logic obtained from product understanding. As a result, cognitive factors, which refer to characteristics of the person that affect performance and learning, frequently influence purchase decisions. (Elida et al., 2021).

The information that is available in society from many different sources, such as advertising, magazines, celebrities, online, friends, family, and bloggers, influences consumers' decisions regarding fashion. Additionally, buying clothing is a serious task that necessitates a deeper level of consumer engagement. Today's society views social influencers as "the most powerful force in the fashion sector," including journalists, celebrities, bloggers, publications, and brand advocates. They influence customers' purchase decisions based on their own opinion, skill, and position and are frequently regarded as subject-matter experts by customers. As a result, social influencers have a significant impact on consumers' purchase decisions and have the power to shape what is considered a trend and a "must have" fashion since people tend to mimic their own style and regard them as industry gurus. So social influencers have a bigger impact on consumers today than they did in the past. (Sudha, M., & Sheena, K., 2017, September)

Conner & Armitage, (1998) found that when a person decides on a future purchase using past purchasing experiences, one may predict that person's future intentions as well.

One of the major drivers of customer preference for online shopping has been the convenience of shopping. (Easterbrook, 1995). (Bhatnagar et al., 2000) discovered in their research that

customers' perceived shopping convenience is a factor that favourably influences online purchasing behaviour. The user has access to this online shopping option every day of the week, 24 hours a day. From a practical standpoint, some customers only use online channels to avoid in-person interactions with salesmen because they feel pressured or uneasy and do not want to be influenced and controlled in the marketplace.

According to findings of (View of SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING AND CUSTOMER ENGAGEMENT, n.d.) Social media marketing has a significant impact on consumers' purchasing decisions. In order to prevent fraud in online purchasing, it is also crucial to consider social media users' happiness while making purchases from business blogs, posts, pages, and groups and to demonstrate authenticity. As part of business ethics and e-ethics, protecting the privacy of our consumers is crucial to gaining their trust and developing a strong brand. Cyberlaw must be created in accordance with this, and measures must be implemented to safeguard users from bogus company identities and to protect their personal information.

The age of the consumer may affect a number of purchasing joys. First, as exploratory and novelty-seeking behaviours are more prevalent among younger consumers, browsers may be younger than other customers (Hoyer et al., 2017). Second, older consumers may appreciate shopping as exercise the most since stores and malls may appeal to them as nice, safe places to roam around (Duncan et al., 1995). Last but not least, older customers might appreciate pampering more than their younger colleagues. As people age, they may experience physical and mental restrictions that limit their ability to buy independently, which makes them cherish personal attention (Lumpkin & Hite, 1988)

Purchasing decisions are problem-solving activities carried out by individuals in selecting appropriate behavioural alternatives from two or more behavioural alternatives and is considered the most appropriate action in buying by first going through the stages of the decision-making process. Therefore, a consumer in making a buying decision has several measurements, namely: Problem Recognition, Information Search, Alternative Evaluation, Purchase Decision, Post-Purchase Behavior.(Anjelika, F. . . , & Sinaga, T. M. . . 2022)

The choice to buy or not to purchase a product or service is made by the consumer, and it is a significant alternative choice for the market.

There are 6 (six) indicators employed, according to Kotler and Keller in Meithiana Indrasari (2019: 74), and they are as follows:

1. Product choice, consumers can make a decision to buy a product or use the money for other purposes.
2. Choice of brand, the buyer must make a decision about which brand to buy.
3. Choice of dealer, the buyer must make a decision which dealer to visit.
4. Time of purchase, consumer decisions in choosing the timing of purchase can vary, for example, once a month or every six months.
5. The number of purchases, consumers can make decisions about how many products to buy at a time.

Chapter Three

Methodology

3.1 Introduction

This chapter is designed to provide information on research design and research methods. The objective of this research method is to find answers to understanding the important factors influencing customers' online purchasing decisions in the fashion clothing for Gen Z consumers of Darjeeling Pulbazar in the district of Darjeeling, West Bengal, India. This study was designed to be a questionnaire-based survey that was created to collect data from consumers who purchase goods and services from online shopping platforms in India.

An online survey with 69 respondents who frequently purchase online in India was done using a quantitative methodology for this study. Qualtrics will collect all the data using an online survey. A few fundamental inquiries, such as those about age, profession, and purchases made on internet marketplaces, will be included in the questionnaire. The responses will be at least 18 years of age. An online survey will be conducted. Participants will be provided with the survey's URL and QR code.

Using a Likert scale, we'll monitor our development. Nevertheless, 100 to 150 people will receive the survey. A score of 1 denotes a significant disagreement, while a score of 5 denotes a strong agreement. In the event when the participant strongly agrees, then most satisfaction is taken into account, and vice versa. Following the completion of data collection, the data will be analysed using SPSS software.

3.2 Conceptual Framework:

Conceptual Framework:

3.3 Research Method

3.3.1 Qualitative vs Quantitative

When seen historically, what is currently referred to as qualitative, or occasionally ethnographic, there has more or less always been interpretative research, also referred to by a variety of different names. (Aspers, 2019). Qualitative research refers to studies of topics that are challenging to measure, such as art history, when discussing different types of research. The goal of qualitative research is to provide a thorough account of some event or unit using a number of techniques, such as in-depth interviews or in-depth analysis of historical sources. King, G., Keohane, R. O., & Verba, S. (2021)

In contrast to qualitative variables and research, quantitative variables and research are defined as "variables or research that can be handled numerically". Quantitative research is everything that is not about numbers from a qualitative perspective, while qualitative research is everything that is quantitative from a qualitative perspective. (Aspers & Corte, 2019).

Research into phenomena in their natural settings using a systematic approach is known as qualitative research, which can focus on a variety of topics such as people's experiences, individual and/or group behaviour, and organisational function. For qualitative research, sample size is not predetermined, unlike in quantitative studies. The process of gathering data typically lasts until there is no longer any fresh knowledge or viewpoints to add. (Das, 2021)

Like quantitative research, it can be used to investigate a wide range of topics, but it tends to concentrate on the meanings and drives that underlie cultural symbols, individual experiences, events, and in-depth comprehension of social world processes. To put it briefly, the focus of qualitative research is on comprehending processes, experiences, and the interpretations that people give to things. Interpretation is a key aspect of qualitative research. It is "multi-method," encompassing the gathering and use of a range of empirical materials and methodologies. It

emphasises both the objective nature of conduct and its subjective meanings, including how individuals see their own attitudes, motivations, behaviour, events, and situations, as well as what people say and do in particular settings and institutions within social and temporal contexts. As a result, it qualifies as an interpretative science. (Aspers & Corte, 2019b)

Although both quantitative and qualitative research have the same overall objective of better understanding the world, their methodology and focus on some ways differ significantly (Becker, 1967) According to (Marchel & Owens, 2007), the primary distinction between the two approaches is exaggerated and does not based on the straightforward "numbers vs words" difference.

3.3.2 Quantitative Research

It's all about numbers in quantitative research. It is about measuring: how much of something there is, how long something has been happening, or about explaining why something happened and perhaps determining whether or to what extent it will continue in the future. Its definition almost always places qualitative research in opposition. (Williams et al., 2021) Quantitative research is described as "a strategy for testing objective ideas by examining the relationship among variables" by (Creswell, 2012). To enable statistical analysis of numbered data, these variables can be measured, often using instruments. According to (Zhang & Zhou, 2011), quantitative research aims to "understand phenomena by gathering numerical form and analysing with the help of mathematically based tools, in particular statistics." Therefore, rather than just identifying them and interpreting the meanings people bring to their own actions, quantitative research focuses on those characteristics of social behaviour that can be quantified and patterned. In quantitative research, the researcher intervenes in the setting of the study in order to identify causal correlations between the variables under study (Burns, 1999).

3.4 SPSS

A popular statistical analysis programme is SPSS. The exploratory process of fundamental statistical analysis and the Kolmogorov-Smirnov process of nonparametric statistical analysis are two of the three test techniques offered by SPSS for the normality test of continuous quantitative data. The most important aspect of statistical analysis is accurately choosing statistical analysis techniques and combining professional expertise to draw findings that are supported by science. (Yang, 2022)

3.5 The respondents and sampling process

3.5.1 Demographic Pattern in Darjeeling

Hill and Plain Regions can be distinguished within the District Darjiling based on physiographic characteristics. Out of the district's 12 Community Development Blocks (CDBs) and 5 Statutory Towns, 4 of the CDBs—Darjeeling-Pulbazar, Rangli Rangliot, Jorebungalow Sukhiapokhri, Kalimpong I, Kalimpong II, Gorubathan, Mirik, and Kurseong—as well as the Statutory Towns—Darjeeling Municipality, Kurseong Municipality, Kalimpong. The district contains 24 Census Towns and a total of 687 villages. (Directorate of Census Operations, West Bengal, 2014)

3.5.2 Population

As per Census 2011, the population of Darjeeling stands at 18,46,823 with 9,37,259 males and 9,09,564 females. Surprisingly, Darjiling district has the greatest sex ratio in the state (970 girls for every 1000 males), and the district maintains the same ranking for rural areas (973) as well. It ranks third (965) and second (1015) in terms of the population of Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes, respectively. (Directorate of Census Operations, West Bengal, 2014)

DISTRICT CENSUS HANDBOOK : DARJILING										
DISTRICT PRIMARY										
Location code number	District/ CD Block/ Town	Total/ Rural/ Urban	Area in Square Kilometre	Number of households	Total population (including institutional and houseless population)			Population in the age-group 0-6		
					Persons	Males	Females	Persons	Males	Females
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
327	Darjiling - District	Total	3,149.00	391,234	1,846,823	937,259	909,564	193,169	98,933	94,236
		Rural	2,995.51	236,694	1,118,860	566,965	551,895	126,773	64,529	62,244
		Urban	153.49	154,540	727,963	370,294	357,669	66,396	34,404	31,992
0001	Darjeeling Pulbazar	Total	416.00	27,470	126,935	63,828	63,107	11,696	6,036	5,660
		Rural	383.71	22,683	105,150	53,078	52,072	9,944	5,127	4,817
		Urban	32.29	4,787	21,785	10,750	11,035	1,752	909	843

District Primary Census Abstract

(Census of India 2011 - West Bengal - Series 20 - Part XII B - District Census Handbook, Darjiling)

Important Statistics						
		State		District		
Number of Villages	Total	40,203		687		
	Inhabited	37,468		616		
	Uninhabited	2,735		71		
Number of Towns	Statutory	129		5		
	Census	780		24		
	Total	909		29		
Number of Households	Normal	20,309,872		389,003		
	Institutional	41,796		1,793		
	Houseless	28,647		438		
Population	Total	Persons	91,276,115		1,846,823	
		Males	46,809,027		937,259	
		Females	44,467,088		909,564	
	Rural	Persons	62,183,113		1,118,860	
		Males	31,844,945		566,965	
		Females	30,338,168		551,895	
	Urban	Persons	29,093,002		727,963	
		Males	14,964,082		370,294	
		Females	14,128,920		357,669	
Percentage Urban Population			31.87		39.42	
Decadal Population Growth 2001-2011						
		Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage	
	Persons	11,099,918	13.84	237,651	14.77	
	Males	5,343,042	12.89	106,615	12.84	
	Females	5,756,876	14.87	131,036	16.83	
Area (in sq Km.)		88752		3149.00		
Density of Population (Persons per sq Km.)		1028		586		
Sex Ratio (Number of females per 1000 males)	Total	950		970		
	Rural	953		973		
	Urban	944		966		

Important Statistics, Darjiling District. India

(Census of India 2011 - West Bengal - Series 20 - Part XII B - District Census Handbook, Darjiling)

3.6 Sample Size

The overall population of Darjiling is 1,846,823, or almost 1.9 million in total, according to Census of India 2011 - West Bengal - Series 20 - Part XII B - District Census Handbook, Darjiling. This population has gradually increased during the year since it was reported. Yamane, T. (1973) formula has been used to calculate the sample size of this research.

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

n - the sample size

N - the population size

E - the acceptable sampling error

The permissible error, according to Taro Yamane's formula, was 0.05. Consequently, the sample size may be determined.

$$n = \frac{1,846,823}{1+1,846,823(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = 400$$

Due to time constraints, it is not possible to gather 400 samples, hence the limitation has been written to provide a summary instead of the recommended sampling size of 400.

3.7 Sampling procedure

The two types of sampling techniques are probability and non-probability techniques (Omair, 2016); Tyrer & Heyman, 2016). Random selection is a component of probability sampling techniques, ensuring that every case in the population has an equal chance of being chosen (Shorten & Moorley, 2014).

In survey research, probability sampling has long been the norm. Unbiased estimations of the population quantities under the sample distribution are provided by analysis that follows the sampling design. The generalizability of sample data is seriously threatened by selection bias, which can be prevented by carefully planned probability sampling and strong cooperation. (Xi et al., 2022). Furthermore, since we are aware of the selection probability for each unit, probability sampling gives a mathematically acceptable framework for evaluating the accuracy of the estimations (Lohr, 2021). Random sampling, systematic sampling, stratified sampling, and cluster sampling are examples of common probability methods. (Elfil, M., & Negida, A. 2017)

From a methodological standpoint, quasi-randomization and superpopulation models are often the two types of methodologies used to draw conclusions from nonprobability samples (Elliott & Valliant, 2017). By determining the inclusion probabilities of the nonprobability sample, the quasi-randomization approach attempts to resemble a probability sampling framework. A reference probability sample is used to calibrate pseudo-weights that are created based on inclusion probabilities (Schonlau, Van Soest, and Kapteyn 2007). The superpopulation model method focuses on simulating the relationship between a result and pertinent covariates before extrapolating the sample to the intended population. The primary distinction between the two strategies is that the former relies on model-based inference conditioning on the gathered sample, while the latter uses design-based inference. A recent methodological advancement called the doubly robust technique also proposes a way to combine the two (Valliant, 2019).

In contrast to qualitative research questions, which can only be addressed by non-probability sampling methods, quantitative research questions can be addressed by either probability or non-probability sampling methods. The advantages and disadvantages of each of the popular probability and non-probability sampling methods are discussed. (Berndt, 2020)

3.7.1 Simple Random Sampling

A sort of probability sampling in which the units making up a population are given numbers is known as simple random sampling. The units that contain those numbers are subsequently included in the sample when a set of random numbers is produced. (Babbie, 2008). For instance, if a simple random sample of 100 people is needed from a sample frame of 8,500 people (listed from 1- 8,500), a simple choice might be made using a computer table of random numbers or another random number generator to obtain a hundred different numbers within the same range. (Adwok, J.2015)

3.8 Research instrument and questionnaires

The research instrument utilised in this study is divided into two sections: the demographic questions and the main study questions. Age, gender, monthly pay, employment position, and educational background are just a few of the demographic inquiries that are asked. And the primary questions cover topics like branding, promotion, place, price, and product.

3.8.1 Closed ended

There are many ways in which open-ended and closed-ended questions differ from one another, particularly in terms of the respondents' roles in providing answers. While open-ended questions permit the responder to voice an opinion without being swayed by the researcher, closed-ended questions restrict the respondent to the set of possibilities being presented (Foddy, 1993: 127).

The respondents to the closed-ended survey are given a scale, a collection of statements expressing attitudes, and other information. In response, students select the number of points on the scale that best expresses their attitude. These scales can be unipolar (such as a 5-point scale ranging from "Not at all satisfied" to "Extremely satisfied") or bipolar (such as a 5-point scale ranging from "Strongly disagree" to "Strongly agree"). The former is based on the idea that attitudes are bipolar entities. The latter makes use of a unipolar construct that simply measures attitude intensity (Krosnick & Fabrigar, 1997).

Despite the benefits of the closed-ended approach that have already been mentioned, this method ignores the cognitive burden that respondents must endure as described by (Tourangeau & Rasinski, 1988). Respondents must first interpret the question, then identify the attitude that is being measured, then recall their beliefs and feelings, and finally relate those beliefs and feelings to the point on the scale that best describes their attitudes.

3.8.2 Likert-scale

Since numerous study claims in applied linguistics have been made using likert-scale surveys, it is crucial to validate our score interpretations. (Yamashita, 2022).

Items in surveys have a stem (e.g., *I always feel that the other students speak the foreign language better than me.*) and several response options (e.g., *strongly agree, agree, neutral,*

disagree, strongly disagree). The response option that best captures the respondents' attitudes, beliefs, and experiences is chosen by the respondents. Despite being widely used in applied linguistics, Likert-scale surveys have some drawbacks. (Brown, 2001; Dörnyei & Taguchi, 2009), best practises are still irrelevant.

Website User Survey

An example questionnaire about a website design, with answers as a Likert scale (wikipedia)

The format of a typical five-level Likert item, for example, could be:

- Strongly agree
- Somewhat agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Somewhat disagree
- Strongly disagree

3.9 Data Collection and gathering procedures

By asking questions to the individuals involved in the issue, data is gathered using questionnaires. Employing a Likert scale to evaluate the responses of the respondents. This scale makes use of a number of question items to measure each respondent's behaviour in response to the question's five choice points.

3.9.1 Primary Data

The product, price, location, promotion, and branding-related questions in the primary data consist of 11 main questions and 24 subquestions. All of the responses are categorised using a

five-point Likert scale: Strongly agree, Somewhat agree, Neither agree nor disagree, Somewhat disagree, and Strongly disagree.

3.9.2 Secondary Data

All types of data from literature reviews, including yearly reports, journals, library, and statistics data, has been used in secondary data.

3.10 Data analysis

3.10.1 Conjoint analysis

Conjoint analysis is used to reveal how people make complex judgements and is based on a number of assumptions. One is that purchase decisions are not based on a single factor, but on several factors “considered jointly” (O'Boyle, E. J., & Dawson, L. E.1992). Conjoint analysis gives insight on the relative significance of product qualities and their relationships with one another. (Walley et al., 2007). Conjoint analysis was created in the domains of mathematical psychology and psychometrics and made popular by Luce and Tukey in their article (1964) The method was then applied to evaluate customer buying decisions.

3.10.2 The variable measurement

In research from Statistics Solutions (2021) There are four different ways to measure a variable: nominal, ordinal, interval, and ratio. (Levels of measurement such as interval and ratio are sometimes known as continuous or scale.)

3.10.3 Four Different Levels of Measurement

In descending order of precision, the four different levels of measurement are:

- **Nominal**–Latin for name only (Republican, Democrat, Green, Libertarian)
- **Ordinal**–Think ordered levels or ranks (small–8oz, medium–12oz, large–32oz)
- **Interval**–Equal intervals among levels (1 dollar to 2 dollars is the same interval as 88 dollars to 89 dollars)
- **Ratio**–Let the “o” in ratio remind you of a zero in the scale (Day 0, day 1, day 2, day 3, ...)

3.11 Pilot Study

The questionnaire is crucial to the study's findings. If the questionnaire is poorly constructed, it won't collect the necessary data or it might collect incomplete data (Brace, 2018). To address this, a pilot questionnaire was given to knowledgeable professionals to confirm its breadth and applicability before being given to Gen Z in Darjeeling Pulbazaar.

A pilot study serves as a replica and test of the primary survey. The fundamental reason for doing a pilot study is to identify any problem in the measurement device, if any exist. The measurement tool used in our current investigation is a questionnaire. Through this pilot study, it is necessary to guarantee the responsiveness and application of the same by examining the validity and reliability of the survey. (Srinivasan & Lohith, 2017)

A pilot study is a limited feasibility study that aims to evaluate several aspects of the approaches anticipated for a bigger, more thorough, or confirmatory investigation. (Arain et al., 2010). A pilot study's main goal is not to provide answers to specific research questions, but rather to prevent researchers from beginning a large-scale study before they are sufficiently familiar with the suggested methodologies, (Polit, D. F., & Beck, C. T. 2008). In brief, Pilot studies are typically used by researchers to assess the suitability of their proposed methods and procedures.

A well-designed and carried out pilot study may also assist researchers in identifying potential confounding factors that were not previously known and assessing the strength of connections between significant variables to assist in sample size calculation. (Polit, D. F., & Beck, C. T. 2008).

Pilot study procedures to improve the internal validity of a questionnaire abstracted from a book *"Health Science Research by Wei Xuan, Katrina Williams, Jennifer K Peat"*

- administer the questionnaire to pilot subjects in exactly the same way as it will be administered in the main study
- ask the subjects for feedback to identify ambiguities and difficult questions
- record the time taken to complete the questionnaire and decide whether it is reasonable
- discard all unnecessary, difficult or ambiguous questions
- assess whether each question gives an adequate range of responses
- establish that replies can be interpreted in terms of the information that is required
- check that all questions are answered
- re-word or re-scale any questions that are not answered as expected
- shorten, revise and, if possible, pilot again.

(Xuan, W., Williams, K., & Peat, J.K. 2001)

Therefore, the pilot study was carried out among a small number of individuals before it was distributed widely to gather data.

Chapter Four

Findings and discussion

4.1 Introduction

The major objective of this study was to identify the four elements of the digital marketing mix and brand influence that have an impact on Gen Z customers' decisions to make purchases through online e-commerce platforms. Additionally, to understand whether they prefer traditional or online purchasing.

Through social media platforms like Facebook Messenger, WhatsApp, and Instagram, the survey was distributed to a number of Gen Z population of the Darjeeling district. With a total of 83 respondents, 69 of which completed the survey.

The closed-ended questions were subjected to Conjoint Analysis and analysed in SPSS.

4.1 Descriptive Statistics:

To explain the fundamental characteristics of the data in a study, descriptive statistics are used. They offer brief summaries of the sample and the measurements. They serve as the foundation for almost all quantitative analyses of data, along with straightforward graphical analysis. Trochim, W. M., & Donnelly, J. P. (2001). And also, Quantitative descriptions are presented in an understandable fashion using descriptive statistics. Many different measurements could be used in a research project. Alternately, we might assess many individuals using any metric. We can rationally simplify massive volumes of data with the use of descriptive statistics. Each descriptive statistic distills a large amount of data into a more concise summary.

4.1.1 Personal data of responses

This section contains a number of survey questions and a report that details the responses that were collected through Qualtrics and analysed by conjoint analysis in SPSS. There are total of five tables used to group survey questionnaires. First, personal demographic questions about their gender, age, monthly income, and more were asked. Then, questions about the four components of the digital marketing mix—product, price, place, and promotion—as well as branding questions followed.

Table 1: Respondents information

Personal Factor	Frequency	Percent (%)
Gender		
Male	29	42.0%
Female	40	58.0%
Total	69	100.0%

Salary		
Less than 15,000 INR	6	8.7%
15,000 - 25,000 INR	14	20.3%
25,000 - 35,000 INR	4	5.8%
35,000 - 45,000 INR	10	14.5%
Prefer not to say	35	50.7%
Total	69	100.0%

Employment Status

Student	37	53.6%
Employed	27	39.1%
Unemployed	1	1.4%
Others	4	5.8%
Total	69	100.0%

Education		
12th Grade or less	8	11.6%
Graduated High School or equivalent	14	20.3%
Bachelor's degree	32	46.4%
Post-graduate degree	15	21.7%
Total	69	100.0%

All the personal respondent's data, including their gender, monthly income, employment position, and educational background, are included in the table above.

- In finding, it came out there are like 29 male with 42% and 40 female with 58% respondents out of 69 total respondents.
- Regarding their monthly income, the majority of the respondents preferred not to disclose. 14 respondents in second place have monthly incomes of 15,000 to 25,000 Indian rupees, and at least only 4 respondents have monthly incomes of 25,000 to 35,000.
- Out of 69 respondents overall, 37 were students, making up 53.6% of the total; the lowest unemployment rate was 1 responder.
- The majority of the 32 respondents had a bachelor's degree or above in terms of education, while the last eight respondents had only completed the 12th grade or less.

Questions on Product:

Research question 1: How often do you buy products (fashion apparel) or services on an e-commerce platform?

And the options were:

- **More than 5 times a month**
- **3 - 4 times a month**
- **1- 2 times a month**
- **1 time a month**
- **Never**

	Frequency	Percent (%)
More than 5 times a month	8	11.6%
3 - 4 times a month	12	17.4%
1 - 2 times a month	29	42.0%

1 time a month	13	18.8%
Never	7	10.1%
Total	69	100.0%

When asked about their typical monthly purchase, the first question revealed that average 42% of respondents' shops online of 1 to 2 a month, while only 7 respondents indicated they did not shop online frequently (10.1%).

Research question 2: **What factors should be thought about when making an online purchase?**

And the options were: (they had to tick accordingly to Likert Scale)

- a) **The design of an app affects the user experience.**
- b) **The ease of use of an app**
- c) **How its products (clothes) are displayed**
- d) **Product availability has a significant effect**
- e) **Product genuity, or if a product is exactly what it appears to be**

a) The design of an app affects the user experience.		
	Frequency	Percent (%)
Strongly agree	36	52.2%

Somewhat agree	24	34.8%
Neither agree nor disagree	6	8.7%
Somewhat disagree	2	2.9%
Strongly disagree	1	1.4%
Total	69	100.0%

b) The ease of use of an app

	Frequency	Percent (%)
Strongly agree	50	72.5%
Somewhat agree	16	23.2%
Neither agree nor disagree	2	2.9%
Somewhat disagree	0	0%
Strongly disagree	1	1.4%
Total	69	100.0%

c) How its products (clothes) are displayed		
	Frequency	Percent
Strongly agree	47	68.1%
Somewhat agree	1	23.2%
Neither agree nor disagree	3	4.3%
Somewhat disagree	3	4.3%
Strongly disagree	0	0%
Total	69	100.0%
d) Product availability has a significant effect		
	Frequency	Percent
Strongly agree	39	56.5%
Somewhat agree	25	36.2%
Neither agree nor disagree	4	5.8%

Somewhat disagree	1	1.4%
Strongly disagree	0	0%
Total	69	100.0%

e) Product genuity, or if a product is exactly what it appears to be

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly agree	58	84.1%
Somewhat agree	8	11.6%
Neither agree nor disagree	1	1.4%
Somewhat disagree	2	2.9%
Strongly disagree	0	0%
Total	69	100.0%

Statistics

	The design of an app affects the user experience.	The ease of use of an app	How its products (clothes) are displayed	Product availability has a significant effect	Product genuity, or if a product is exactly what it appears to be
Valid	69	69	69	69	69
Missing	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	6.67	6.35	6.45	6.52	6.23
Std. Deviation	.869	.682	.777	.678	.622

The components in the first marketing mix, "Product," were the subject of questions in table no. 2. They significantly agreed (52.2%) that "the design of an app affects the user experience." 72.5% strongly agreed that an app was "ease of use," and 68.1% strongly agreed that "its products were shown in the app." The "product availability" accounted for 56.5% of the total, and "product genuity," with a substantial share of 84.1%, was the last element considered when deciding whether to make an online purchase.

Research question 3: **What concerns more to you when making an online purchase?**

And the options were: (they had to tick accordingly to Likert Scale)

- a) **Price of a product (clothes) is more important than its quality.**
- b) **Quality of a product is more important than its price.**

a) Price of a product (clothes) is more important than its quality.		
	Frequency	Percent (%)

Strongly agree	15	21.7%
Somewhat agree	25	36.2%
Neither agree nor disagree	13	18.8%
Somewhat disagree	8	11.6%
Strongly disagree	8	11.6%
Total	69	100.0%

b) Quality of a product is more important than its price.

	Frequency	Percent (%)
Strongly agree	34	49.3%
Somewhat agree	21	30.4%
Neither agree nor disagree	10	14.5%
Somewhat disagree	3	4.3%
Strongly disagree	1	1.4%

Total	69	100.0%
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Statistics		
	Price of a product (clothes) is more important than its quality.	Quality of a product is more important than its price.
Valid	69	69
Missing	0	0
Mean	7.55	6.78
Std. Deviation	1.278	.953

The second component of the digital marketing mix, "Price," is discussed in table 3 above. Analysis revealed that, with a 49.3%, a product's quality is more significant than its price.

Research question 4: **Which form of delivery do you prefer the most?**

And the options were:(they had to tick accordingly to Likert Scale)

- a) Cash on delivery**

- b) Online payment
- c) Free return policy
- d) Free tracking
- e) Security

a) Cash on delivery		
	Frequency	Percent (%)
Strongly agree	24	34.8%
Somewhat agree	19	27.5%
Neither agree nor disagree	20	29.0%
Somewhat disagree	3	4.3%
Strongly disagree	3	4.3%
Total	69	100.0%
b) Online payment		
	Frequency	Percent (%)
Strongly agree	23	33.3%

Somewhat agree	31	44.9%
Neither agree nor disagree	10	14.5%
Somewhat disagree	2	2.9%
Strongly disagree	3	4.3%
Total	69	100.0%

c) Free return policy

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly agree	64	92.8%
Somewhat agree	2	2.9%
Neither agree nor disagree	3	4.3%
Somewhat disagree	0	0%
Strongly disagree	0	0%
Total	69	100.0%

d) Free tracking		
	Frequency	Percent
Strongly agree	58	84.1%
Somewhat agree	7	10.1%
Neither agree nor disagree	2	2.9%
Somewhat disagree	1	1.4%
Strongly disagree	1	1.4%
Total	69	100.0%
e) Security		
	Frequency	Percent
Strongly agree	60	87.0
Somewhat agree	8	11.6
Neither agree nor disagree	0	0

Somewhat disagree	1	1.4
Strongly disagree	0	0
Total	69	100.0%

Statistics					
	Cash on delivery	Online payment	Free return policy	Free tracking	Security
Valid	69	69	69	69	69
Missing	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	7.16	7.00	6.12	6.26	6.16
Std. Deviation	1.093	1.000	.438	.721	.474

Research question 5: **Which shopping method do you like using the most?**

And the options were: (they had to tick accordingly to Likert Scale)

- a) **Online shopping**
- b) **In-store shopping**

a) Online shopping		
	Frequency	Percent
Strongly agree	32	46.4%
Somewhat agree	21	30.4%
Neither agree nor disagree	13	18.0%
Somewhat disagree	3	4.3%
Strongly disagree	0	0%
Total	69	100.0%
b) In-store shopping		
	Frequency	Percent
Strongly agree	25	36.2%
Somewhat agree	34	49.3%

Neither agree nor disagree	10	14.5%
Somewhat disagree	0	0%
Strongly disagree	0	0%
Total	69	100.0%

Statistics		
	Online shopping	In-store shopping
Valid	69	69
Missing	0	0
Mean	6.81	6.78
Std. Deviation	.896	.683

Research question 6: **Which online platform do you use most frequently to shop (fashion apparel) online?**

And the options were:

- **Amazon India**
- **Meesho**
- **Myntra**
- **Ajio**

- Other

Online platform		
	Frequency	Percent (%)
Amazon India	31	44.9%
Meesho	3	4.3%
Myntra	16	23.2%
Ajio	4	5.8%
Other	15	21.7%
Total	69	100.0%

Statistics	
	Online platform
Valid	69
Missing	0

Mean	2.55
Std. Deviation	1.614

The third "Place" in the digital marketing mix was discussed in table number 4. When evaluating 92.8% of their purchases, "free return policy" was shown to be the most important delivery choice element, followed by "security" at 87% and "free tracking" at 84.1%.

Following the question on whether they preferred shopping in-stores or online, 46.4% of the respondents said they preferred online shopping, while just 36.2% preferred shopping in-stores.

Finally, when asked which of the online ecommerce platforms they favoured the most to shop online, a staggering 44.9% said they chose Amazon India.

Questions on Promotion:

Research question 7: **Social media influence (Instagram influencers promoting products)**

And the options were: (they had to tick accordingly to Likert Scale)

- **Likert scale of Strongly agree, somewhat agree, neither agree nor disagree, somewhat disagree, and strongly disagree**

• Social media influence (Instagram influencers promoting products)		
	Frequency	Percent (%)
Strongly agree	24	34.8%
Somewhat agree	27	39.1%

Neither agree nor disagree	12	17.4%
Somewhat disagree	4	5.8%
Strongly disagree	2	2.9%
Total	69	100.0%

Statistics	
	Social media influence (Instagram influencers promoting products)
Valid	69
Missing	0
Mean	7.3
Std. Deviation	1.014

Research question 8: What factor of promotions has a significant impact on consumers' purchasing decisions?

And the options were: (they had to tick accordingly to Likert Scale)

- Flash Sales
- Promotional coupons
- Buy 1 Get 1 Free
- Loyalty Points

a) Flash Sales		
	Frequency	Percent (%)
Strongly agree	28	40.6%
Somewhat agree	31	44.9%
Neither agree nor disagree	7	10.1%
Somewhat disagree	3	4.3%
Strongly disagree	0	0%
Total	69	100.0%
b) Promotional coupons		
	Frequency	Percent (%)
Strongly agree	33	47.8%

Somewhat agree	29	42.0%
Neither agree nor disagree	6	8.7%
Somewhat disagree	1	1.4%
Strongly disagree	0	0%
Total	69	100.0%

c) Buy 1 Get 1 Free

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly agree	43	62.3%
Somewhat agree	18	26.1%
Neither agree nor disagree	3	4.3%
Somewhat disagree	4	5.8%
Strongly disagree	1	1.4%
Total	69	100.0%

d) Loyalty Points		
	Frequency	Percent
Strongly agree	35	50.7%
Somewhat agree	20	29.0%
Neither agree nor disagree	9	13.0%
Somewhat disagree	5	7.2%
Strongly disagree	0	0%
Total	69	100.0%

Statistics				
	Flash Sales	Promotional coupons	Buy 1 Get 1 Free	Loyalty Points
Valid	69	69	69	69
Missing	0	0	0	0

Mean	6.78	6.64	6.58	6.77
Std. Deviation	.802	.707	.930	.942

When asked how social networking platforms like Instagram affect their decision to make an online purchase, 39.1% said that they have some agreement with this statement, while 34.8% expressed a strong agreement. This falls under the fourth element of the digital marketing mix, "Promotion".

When asked which promotional aspect had the biggest effects on completing an online purchase, 62.3% ranked "Buy 1 Get 1 Free" as the most important, with "Loyalty points" coming in second with 50.7%

Questions on Branding:

Research question 9: **When making an online purchase, what brand do you consider the most?**

And the options were:

- **H&M**
- **Zara**
- **Forever 21**
- **Mango**
- **Other**

● what brand do you consider the most?		
	Frequency	Percent (%)
H&M	38	55.1%
Zara	14	20.3%

Forever 21	1	1.4%
Mango	4	5.8%
Other	12	17.4%
Total	69	100.0%

Statistics	
	What brand do you consider the most?
Valid	69
Missing	0
Mean	2.10
Std. Deviation	1.545

Research question 10: **What brand characteristics should be considered when shopping online?**

And the options were: (they had to tick accordingly to Likert Scale)

- a) Brand loyalty
- b) Brand image
- c) Other customers' reviews

a) Brand loyalty		
	Frequency	Percent (%)
Strongly agree	44	63.8%
Somewhat agree	20	29.0%
Neither agree nor disagree	4	5.8%
Somewhat disagree	0	0%
Strongly disagree	1	1.4%
Total	69	100.0%
b) Brand image		
	Frequency	Percent (%)
Strongly agree	40	58.0%
Somewhat agree	21	30.4%

Neither agree nor disagree	5	7.2%
Somewhat disagree	3	4.3%
Strongly disagree	0	0%
Total	69	100.0%

- **Other customers' reviews**

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly agree	49	71.0%
Somewhat agree	17	24.6%
Neither agree nor disagree	3	4.3%
Somewhat disagree	0	0%
Strongly disagree	0	0%
Total	69	100.0%

Statistics			
	Brand loyalty	Brand image	Other customers' review
Valid	69	69	69
Missing	0	0	0
Mean	6.46	6.58	6.33
Std. Deviation	.739	.812	.560

Research question 11: How important does a brand's recognition affect your trust in online shopping?

And the options were: (they had to tick accordingly to Likert Scale)

- a. The brand is well known**
- b. The brand is industry's biggest seller online**
- c. The brand has high volume of sales online**

a) The brand is well known		
	Frequency	Percent (%)
Strongly agree	36	52.2%
Somewhat agree	26	37.7%

Neither agree nor disagree	6	8.7%
Somewhat disagree	1	1.4%
Strongly disagree	0	0%
Total	69	100.0%

b) The brand is industry’s biggest seller online

	Frequency	Percent (%)
Strongly agree	32	46.4%
Somewhat agree	24	34.8%
Neither agree nor disagree	10	14.5%
Somewhat disagree	3	14.5%
Strongly disagree	0	0%
Total	69	100.0%

c) The brand has high volume of sales online

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly agree	26	37.7%
Somewhat agree	29	42.0%
Neither agree nor disagree	14	20.3%
Somewhat disagree	0	0%
Strongly disagree	0	0%
Total	69	100.0%

Statistics			
	The brand is well known	The brand is industry's biggest seller online	The brand has high volume of sales online
Valid	69	69	69
Missing	0	0	0
Mean	6.59	6.77	6.83

Std. Deviation	.714	.860	.747
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In the final table of Branding, H&M received a remarkable 55.1% of the vote when asked which of the following brands they prefer to purchase via online platforms, followed by Zara with 20.3%.

Following the questions on branding, the respondents were asked which characteristics—namely, brand loyalty, brand image, or other customers' reviews—they would prefer the most when making an online purchasing decision. With the highest percentage of votes (71%), "other customers' review" was deemed to be the most crucial factor in any online purchase.

Last but not least, when asked how much a brand's reputation affects consumers' trust when they shop online, the response "Brand is well known" came in first place with 52.2%, followed by "brand is industry's biggest seller online" with 46.4%, and "brand has the highest volume of sales online" with only 37.7%.

Chapter Five

Conclusion and Recommendation

5.1 Introduction:

The important conclusions drawn from the survey data are outlined in this chapter. The chapter also discusses the research's strengths and contributions, as well as its limitations. Finally, this chapter also includes advice for the present and the future.

5.2 Conclusion:

The purpose of the research is clearly explained in the first chapter of the introduction.

This research was designed to understand the important factors influencing customers' online purchasing decisions in the fashion clothing for Gen Z consumers of Darjeeling Pulbazar in the district of Darjeeling, West Bengal, India.

In order to determine how their existence or absence in an online shopping environment influences customer happiness, this study looks at how consumers perceive the following online purchasing features; What types of delivery services do customers prefer: cash on delivery, online payments, a no-fee return policy, or product tracking? Additionally, what elements of the app's user experience do they value most, such as discounts and promotions, convenience of use, the presentation of the app's wide range of products, and customer reviews? What impact does brand image have on consumer choice in terms of purchases?

It has been carefully created with concise definitions such as of Gen Z, is a generation of individuals born between the mid -1990s and the early 2010s according to Generation Z - Affiliate Marketing Product Review Site", 2021.

And descriptions of specific terminology and locations like, Darjeeling, the location of the survey, is a northern district of the state of West Bengal in eastern India and is well-known for its stunning Himalayan hill station as well as Darjeeling tea. It has been given the distinction of

being the queen of all hill stations in the country. (Sensonmedia's Darjeeling District Information, n.d.)

To offer readers a thorough understanding of what the researcher has been attempting to find out, where they can find that information, and who the intended respondents are.

A number of the research questions and the study's goals were addressed prior to beginning, and I believe the following analysis has satisfactorily addressed them.

Following the main research question.

“What are the main factors in the Digital marketing mix that influence customers' online fashion clothing purchasing decisions in the Darjeeling district of India?”

All elements are significant from their perspective, but this research's findings indicate that **92.8%** of Gen Z customers rely their online purchase decisions on the *“free return policy,”* demonstrating the significance of delivery in their thoughts. After that, they also take into account *“Product Genuity,”* which has a sizable proportion of **84.1%** and is taken into account by customers when determining whether to make an online purchase because there have been numerous instances of fraud in online sales recently. In addition, **71%** of respondents said that *“other customers' reviews”* were important when making an online purchase, making that information even more important. Last but not least, **52.2%** of respondents agreed that Gen Z buyers tend to place greater trust in a company's *“well-known brand”* when making a decision to buy something online.

“This research aims to identify and evaluate the most important factors in the Digital Marketing Mix in online purchasing decisions in the Fashion Clothes affecting Gen Z consumers in Darjeeling Pulbazar in the district of Darjeeling, West Bengal, India”.

According to research results, the “free return policy” element from the Digital Marketing Mix, which falls under the “Price” factor, is without a doubt the most crucial one for Gen Z buyers when making online shopping decisions because it received the highest score of 92.8%.

Despite being inconsistent when being questioned.

“What concerns more to you when making an online purchase?”

with their options of choices.

- *Price of a product (clothes) is more important than its quality.*
- *Quality of a product is more important than its price.*

Interestingly, the results of the analysis showed that a product's quality had a greater impact on consumers than its price, with a 49.3% rating.

Coming towards the objectives of this research dissertation:

- *Is to understand what factors in the Digital Marketing Mix is more important for Gen Z in online purchasing*

The results of this study show that **92.8%** of Gen Z customers base their decisions to buy products online on the "**free return policy**," highlighting the importance of delivery in their minds as an aspect of the Digital Marketing Mix that falls under the "**Price**" category.

- *Is to understand the perspective of Gen Z consumers towards online purchasing.*

Surprisingly, the opinions of Gen Z customers regarding online purchases and traditional in-store shopping did not differ that significantly, as the results of this research clearly demonstrate. About 46.4% of Gen Z customers prefer online shopping, while about 36.2% still favour traditional in-store shopping. This could be the reason that people still like to experience traditional shopping style, where they could feel the fabric, try on, look with their naked eyes and then make the decision of purchasing the product.

- *Is to understand what factors in brand influence in making decisions in online purchasing*

When a "Brand is Well Known," Gen Z shoppers are drawn in and consider making a purchase because they believe in the brand's ingenuity. As a result of the research's findings, the first-place response, "Brand is well known," received 52.2% of the votes.

- *Is to understand whether Gen Z customers prefer to shop online or in-store*

In the second objective it was already mentioned Gen Z consumers prefer online purchasing approximately 46.4% of the time, while traditional in-store shopping is still preferred by roughly 36.2%. As a result, there is still much that can be improved upon in online eCommerce platforms in order to grow and draw in clients who use online platforms to make purchases.

Numerous well-written works have been studied in order for any reader to gain a general understanding of the topic chosen for this research. It has also been effectively carried out, and after careful analysis, the findings have provided all the pertinent responses to the aims and study question.

The Digital Marketing Mix, E-marketing, Gen Z, the Purchase Decision-Making Style of Gen Z, Brand Influence, Fashion Apparel, Locations (both online and offline merchants), and Purchasing Decision have all been covered in Chapter 2 of the Literature Review.

Butler defined marketing in 1911 as "everything the promoter of a product has to do prior to his actual use of salesmen and advertising," according to (Silverman, 1995) A Marketing Mix the Historical Context and Development of the Marketing Mix.

Going furthermore in 4Ps, (Constantinides, 2006) asserts that the term "product" refers to all of the elements and facets necessary to deliver a service that adds value to the client. Depending on the needs of the clients, products may differ in a number of ways. A customer's willingness to spend money on a good or service determines its pricing. The management of various expenses suffered by consumers in order to achieve the advantages from providing the services is also shown by the price and other costs of the service sector, according to Davies & Brush (1997). Place refers to administrative choices regarding the locations of consumers' service delivery channels, which may include electronic or physical distribution methods (Davies & Brush, 1997). One method for grabbing customers' attention is through promotion. It comes in the shape of a synthesis of the physical characteristics of the store, which are divided into four groups: the exterior, the general interior, the store layout, and the interior display, which comprises the store's architecture, layout, lighting, display, colour, and aroma. (F. Anjelika, T. M. Sinaga, & Co., 2022).

For Branding, a consumer's perception of a business is called brand image, and it is based on their memories of a product and their feelings toward the business.

A consumer's decision to buy something is the result of the thought process that leads them from realising they have a need to exploring options and choosing a particular brand and item. Consumers become aware of and identify their demands through this process, which also involves learning how to best meet those needs, weighing the pros and drawbacks of various possibilities, making a purchasing decision, and reviewing that decision (1921, Millwood).

A quantitative methodology was used to conduct an online survey of 69 respondents who commonly shop online in India for this study. Using an online survey, Qualtrics gathers all the data. There were a few basic questions on the form, including ones regarding age, career, and purchases done on online marketplaces. The respondents must be at least 18 years old to respond. A survey was carried out online. The URL and QR code for the survey will be made available to participants.

Kept track of advancement using a Likert scale. But only 100 to 150 people got the survey. A score of 1 indicates a substantial difference, whereas a score of 5 indicates a strong agreement. The participant's level of agreement was taken into consideration, and vice versa, if they strongly concur. Following the conclusion of data collection, SPSS software was used to analyse the data.

A quantitative methodology was employed to conduct an online survey of people who frequently shop online in India for this study. Qualtrics will use an online survey to collect all the data. It was distributed to collect data via social media such as WhatsApp, Instagram and Facebook Messenger the survey's URL and QR code. Progress has been gauged using a Likert scale. The data been analysed using SPSS software after data collection is finished.

Furthermore, Research method there explain difference between Qualitative vs Quantitative analysis. When addressing different sorts of research, investigations of subjects that are difficult to assess, like art history, are referred to as qualitative research. In addition to Verba and

Keohane, King, G. (2021). Quantitative variables and research are described as "variables or research that can be handled mathematically" in contrast to qualitative variables and research (Aspers & Corte, 2019).

Yamane, T. (1973) formula has been used to calculate the sample size of this research. According to Omair (2016) and Tyrer & Heyman (2016), there are two different types of sampling procedures: probability and non-probability techniques. Simple random sampling is a type of probability sampling in which the constituents of a population are assigned numbers.

Age, gender, monthly income, employment status, and educational background are just a few of the demographic questions that are addressed. The research instrument that was used in this study is broken up into two sections: the demographic questions and the major study questions. And the main inquiries deal with matters like product, place, pricing, place, and promotion.

An evaluation scale, a set of statements representing attitudes, and other data are provided to the survey participants in the closed-ended manner. These scales can be unipolar (such as a 5-point scale ranging from "Not at all satisfied" to "Extremely satisfied") or bipolar (such as a 5-point scale ranging from "Strongly disagree" to "Strongly agree") (Krosnick & Fabrigar, 1997). It is important to validate our score interpretations because many study claims in applied linguistics have been made using likert-scale questionnaires. (Yamashita, 2022).

The 11 main questions and 24 subquestions that pertain to the products, prices, locations, promotions, and branding are included in the primary data. On a five-point Likert scale, each reaction is categorised: Strongly agree, A little bit of both, A little bit of neither, A little bit of disagree, and A lot of disagree. Secondary data have used all kinds of data from literature reviews, such as information from annual reports, journals, libraries, and statistics. Conjoint analysis is a technique that reveals how complicated judgments are made by individuals and is predicated on a variety of suppositions. One is that multiple elements are "examined jointly" while making a buying decision rather than relying just on one component (O'Boyle, E. J., & Dawson, L. E. 1992).

A pilot study is a small-scale feasibility study that seeks to assess a number of the methods expected to be used in a larger, more in-depth, or confirmatory inquiry. (2010) Arain et al. The primary objective of a pilot study is to deter researchers from starting a large-scale study before they are fully comfortable with the suggested methodology, not to provide answers to specific research problems (Polit, D. F., & Beck, C. T. 2008). As a result, the pilot research was conducted before it was made freely available to collect data on a smaller group of people.

And lastly on findings and discussion, Descriptive statistics are employed to describe the basic properties of the data in a study. Brief summaries of the sample and the measurements are provided. Along with simple graphical analysis, they act as the cornerstone for practically all quantitative studies of data. Donnelly, J. P., and W. M. Trochim (2001). A list of survey questions, together with a report describing the replies, were gathered using Qualtrics and examined using conjoint analysis in SPSS. To aggregate survey questionnaires, a total of five tables are used. Their gender, age, monthly income, and other personal demographic details

were first inquired about. Following that, questions about the four elements of the digital marketing mix (product, pricing, place, and promotion) as well as inquiries about branding were asked.

5.3 Strength and research contribution:

With the help of this study, readers will have a thorough knowledge of how Gen Z buyers think about buying in general and online shopping in particular, as well as how they choose which products to buy online via online eCommerce platforms. The future researcher or seeker who wants to comprehend how Gen Z, particularly of an area of Darjeeling Pulbazaar, District Darjeeling, West Bengal, India, will also have a clear grasp and will help their subsequent research.

5.4 Practical implication:

In order to improve their business in the modern digital world, eCommerce sellers will gain some useful perspective on how and where they should work hard and concentrate. As a result, even tiny traditional consumers can improve their businesses in their own ways. They also gain insight into what Gen Z consumers truly look for when buying any goods.

5.5 Future recommendation:

I continue to think that every online e-commerce platform should put "ease of use" of an app as a top priority when deciding how to best sell its products. Second, the majority of e-commerce sites ought to offer a free return policy, or at the very least charge a minimal fee for doing so. Brand awareness is also essential if you want to reach a large audience.

Based on these findings, future researchers should think about incorporating more of the other Ps from the digital marketing mix, namely People, Process, and Physical Evidence, to further their comprehension of the details. Because just the first four components of the digital marketing mix—product, price, place, and promotion—as well as branding have been examined in this dissertation, it is not comprehensive.

Although this research has been done properly and gives some clear findings on how current Gen Z online shoppers think while making an online purchasing yet future research might focus on more in-depth interviews and even more questionnaires to better understand how Gen Z

consumers make decisions about making purchases through online eCommerce platforms. This would help researchers better comprehend the significance of these findings.

Also it would be great if many eCommerce platform could adapt Artificial Intelligence (AI) to enhance and strengthen their business. The way organisations run has evolved as a result of disruptive technologies like the internet of things, big data analytics, blockchain, and artificial intelligence. Artificial intelligence (AI) is the last technical change agent among disruptive technologies and has the greatest potential to transform marketing. International interpreters are attempting to determine the fashionable fit AI results for their marketing purposes. (Desai & Ganatra, 2022). The modern world has recently accepted AI significantly and has employed it in the marketing, social media, and e-commerce sectors. AI continues to revolutionise and advance the cause of technology, from self-driving cars to online shopping venues and e-commerce. There has been an effort to decolonize AI, where the idea could be more advantageous for all users than a specific function. There is evidence that AI will change certain aspects of the economy, industry, current jobs, and how we live. The relationship between IoT, machine learning, big data, and analytics must be taken into consideration in order to fully comprehend AI, its difficulties, and how it is applied to other phenomena such as e-commerce. The way we purchase online has changed as a result of the development of many AI technologies and capabilities over the years. (Malapane & Ndlovu, 2022)

Augmented Reality (AR) can be of great innovative approach for the eCommerce platform for further broadening business. AR has a lot of potential in the retail industry, particularly for e-commerce. Even if e-commerce is increasingly popular, some purchases still call for buyers to have a little more background knowledge. Because of this, it could be challenging to sell some product types online. A DTC furniture shop named Burrow developed an AR application that lets consumers customise and arrange 3D representations of Burrow sofas in their own living rooms in response to this need. (Kalmkar et al., 2022). Nowadays, a lot of consumers pre-shop online. This is done so that, thanks to 3D augmented and immersive experiences, consumers can easily study, try on, and experience items whenever they want, from anywhere. The results are increased revenue and brand satisfaction. 3D commerce refers to websites and mobile applications that incorporate 3D models for augmented reality (AR). The goal is to provide prospective buyers and clients with a visual, interactive 3D depiction of the goods.

Limitation:

In quantitative research, collecting data from an entire population of a study is impractical in many instances. There were various restrictions when performing this research, but the most important one was the time constraint. Because of the time constraints, even after reading through numerous other research papers, it was not possible to include everything in this research report.

Due to the size of Darjiling and the district it is located in, as well as the fact that Darjeeling Pulbazaar is still larger than the area being investigated, it was impossible to complete the survey in its entirety in the allotted time.

Thirdly, the number of respondents for the online survey was less than anticipated due to the time limit itself. However, I was able to find a way to get just enough people to participate in the survey.

References:

Abdul Lasi, M. B., & Mohamed Salim, S. (2020, October 1). THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN E-MARKETING MIX STRATEGY AND INTEGRATED MARKETING COMMUNICATION: A CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK. *International Journal of Engineering Applied Sciences and Technology*, 5(6), 40–48.[Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.33564/ijeast.2020.v05i06.007> [Accessed on August 20, 2022]

Adwok, J. (2015). Probability sampling-a guideline for quantitative health care research. *Annals of African Surgery*, 12(2). [Online] Available from: [Probability Sampling - A Guideline for Quantitative Health Care Research | Annals of African Surgery \(ajol.info\)](https://ajol.info/article/view/114444) [Accessed on November, 2, 2022]

Amazon: *What We Do*. (2022). US About Amazon. [Online] Available from: <https://www.aboutamazon.com/what-we-do> [Accessed on August 16, 2022]

Anjelika, F. . . , & Sinaga, T. M. . . (2022). Influence of Marketing MIX 4P (Product, Price, Place, Promotion) On Purchase Decision at PT. Alfa Scorpii Setia Budi Branch Medan . *Jurnal Mantik*, 5(4), 2239-2246. [Online] Available from: <https://iocscience.org/ejournal/index.php/mantik/article/view/1966> [Accessed on October 28, 2022]

Arora, N., & Aggarwal, A. (2018, March 5). The role of perceived benefits in formation of online shopping attitude among women shoppers in India. *South Asian Journal of Business Studies*, 7(1), 91–110. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1108/sajbs-04-2017-0048> [Accessed on October 2, 2022]

Arain, M., Campbell, M. J., Cooper, C. L., & Lancaster, G. A. (2010). What is a pilot or feasibility study? A review of current practice and editorial policy. *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, 10(1). [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2288-10-67> [Accessed on November, 5, 2022]

Aspers, P. (2019, February 27). *What is Qualitative in Qualitative Research*. SpringerLink. [Online] Available from: https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11133-019-9413-7?error=cookies_not_supported&code=e6cab60b-5167-4d23-9800-3a0416ec728d [Accessed on October 29, 2022]

Aspers, P., & Corte, U. (2019). What is Qualitative in Qualitative Research. *Qualitative Sociology*, 42(2), 139–160. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11133-019-9413-7> [Accessed on October 29, 2022]

Bakewell, C., & Mitchell, V. (2003, February 1). Generation Y female consumer decision-making styles. *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, 31(2), 95–106. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1108/09590550310461994> [Accessed on September, 28, 2022]

Babbie, R. (2008). *The Basics of Social Research*. Thomson/Wadsworth.

Becker, H. S. (1967). Whose Side Are We On? *Social Problems*, 14(3), 239–247. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.2307/799147> [Accessed on October 29, 2022]

Berndt, A. E. (2020). Sampling Methods. *Journal of Human Lactation*, 36(2), 224–226. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0890334420906850> [Accessed on November, 2, 2022]

Bhatnagar, A., Misra, S., & Rao, H. R. (2000, November). On risk, convenience, and Internet shopping behavior. *Communications of the ACM*, 43(11), 98–105. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1145/353360.353371> [Accessed on October 3, 2022]

Biswas, A., & Blair, E. A. (1991). Contextual Effects of Reference Prices in Retail Advertisements. *Journal of Marketing*, 55(3), 1–12. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.2307/1252143> [Accessed on October 4, 2022]

Brace, I. (2018). *Questionnaire Design: How to Plan, Structure and Write Survey Material for Effective Market Research*. Kogan Page, Limited.

Brynjolfsson, E., & Smith, M. D. (2000, April). Frictionless Commerce? A Comparison of Internet and Conventional Retailers. *Management Science*, 46(4), 563–585. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.46.4.563.12061> [Accessed on October 4, 2022]

Brown, J. D. (2001). Using surveys in language programs. Cambridge university press.

Burns, A. (1999). *Collaborative Action Research for English Language Teachers*. Cambridge University Press.

Census Department | Darjeeling District, Government of West Bengal | India. (n.d.). [Online] Available from: <https://darjeeling.gov.in/census-department/> [Accessed on September, 12, 2022]

Chang, C. (2011, August). The Effect of the Number of Product Subcategories on Perceived Variety and Shopping Experience in an Online Store. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 25(3), 159–168.[Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intmar.2011.04.001> [Accessed on October, 6, 2022]

Chaffey, D., & Ellis-Chadwick, F. (2012). *Digital Marketing: Strategy, Implementation and Practice* (5th ed.). Pearson Education.

Cox, A. D., Cox, D., & Anderson, R. D. (2005, March). Reassessing the pleasures of store shopping. *Journal of Business Research*, 58(3), 250–259. [Online] Available from: [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0148-2963\(03\)00160-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0148-2963(03)00160-7) [Accessed on October, 6, 2022]

Conner, M., & Armitage, C. J. (1998, August). Extending the Theory of Planned Behavior: A Review and Avenues for Further Research. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 28(15), 1429–1464.[Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1559-1816.1998.tb01685.x> [Accessed on September, 30, 2022]

Constantinides, E. (2014, April 22). Constantinides E., 2006, *The Marketing Mix Revisited: Towards the 21st Century Marketing*, *Journal of Marketing Management*, vol. 22, nr 3 -4, pp 407 – 438. [Online] Available from: https://www.academia.edu/219880/Constantinides_E._2006_The_Marketing_Mix_Revisited_Towards_the_21st_Century_Marketing_Journal_of_Marketing_Management_vol._22_nr_3_-4_pp_407_438 [Accessed on September, 29, 2022]

Creswell, J. W. (2012). *Educational Research: Planning, Conducting, and Evaluating Quantitative and Qualitative Research*. Pearson.

Customer retention and the mediating role of perceived value in retail industry | Emerald Insight. (2018, February 12). Emerald Insights. [Online] Available from: <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/WJEMSD-06-2017-0035/full/html> [Accessed on July 16, 2022]

Darjeeling District Information-Sensonmedia. (n.d.). [Online] Available from: https://www.sensonmedia.net/darjeeling_information.html [Accessed on September, 11, 2022]

Darjeeling District , West Bengal. (n.d.). IndiaNetzone.com. [Online] Available from: https://www.indianetzone.com/19/darjeeling_west_bengal.htm [Accessed on September, 12, 2022]

Das, M. K. (2021). An Introduction to Qualitative and Mixed Methods Study Designs in Health Research. *Indian Pediatrics*, 59(5), 416–423. [Online] Available from: [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13312-022-2523-4> [Accessed on October, 27, 2022]

Davies, W., & Brush, K. E. (1997, January). High-tech industry marketing: The elements of a sophisticated global strategy. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 26(1), 1–13. [Online] Available from: [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0019-8501\(96\)00073-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0019-8501(96)00073-9) [Accessed on September, 22, 2022]

Devi, E. B. A STUDY ON EFFECT OF COVID-19 ON DIGITAL MARKETING. *COVID 19: Impact and Response Volume VII*, 41

De Chernatony, L., & Dall'Olmo Riley, F. (1998). Defining a "brand": Beyond the literature with experts' interpretations. *Journal of marketing Management*, 14(5), 417-443.

Desai, P., & Ganatra, K. (2022). Artificial Intelligence In Strengthening The Operations Of Ecommerce Based Business. *2022 Interdisciplinary Research in Technology and Management (IRTM)*. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1109/irtm54583.2022.9791598> [Accessed on September, 22, 2022]

Directorate of Census Operations, West Bengal. (2014). *Census of India 2011 - West Bengal - Series 20 - Part XII B - District Census Handbook, Darjiling*. Censusindia.gov.in. <https://censusindia.gov.in/nada/index.php/catalog/1329> [Accessed on November, 2, 2022]

Djelic, M. L., & Ainamo, A. (1999, October). The Coevolution of New Organizational Forms in the Fashion Industry: A Historical and Comparative Study of France, Italy, and the United States. *Organization Science*, 10(5), 622–637.[Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1287/orsc.10.5.622> [Accessed on September, 30, 2022]

Dörnyei, Z., & Taguchi, T. (2009). *Questionnaires in second language research: Construction, administration, and processing*. Routledge.

Doyle, P., & Stern, P. (2006). *Marketing management and strategy*. Pearson Education.

Duncan, H. H., Travis, S. S., & McAuley, W. J. (1995, March). An Emergent Theoretical Model for Interventions Encouraging Physical Activity (Mall Walking) Among Older Adults. *Journal of Applied Gerontology*, 14(1), 64–77. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1177/073346489501400105> [Accessed on September, 27, 2022]

Easterbrook, G. (1995, April 1). *A Moment on the Earth: The Coming Age of Environmental Optimism* (First Edition). Viking Adult.

E-commerce in India: Industry Overview, Market Size & Growth | IBEF. (n.d.). India Brand Equity Foundation. [Online] Available from: <https://www.ibef.org/industry/ecommerce> [Accessed on September, 28, 2022]

Elida, T., Rahardjo, W., & Raharjo, A. (2021). Online Shop Consumer Purchasing Decision: A Study on The Significance of Self-Esteem and Marketing Mix. *Jurnal Manajemen Indonesia*, 21(2), 161–170. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.25124/jmi.v21i2.2751> [Accessed on August, 25, 2022]

Elfil, M., & Negida, A. (2017). Sampling methods in Clinical Research; an Educational Review. *Emergency (Tehran, Iran)*, 5(1), e52. [Online] Available from: [Sampling methods in Clinical Research; an Educational Review - PMC \(nih.gov\)](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31111111/) [Accessed on November, 2, 2022]

Elliott, M. R., & Valliant, R. (2017). Inference for Nonprobability Samples. *Statistical Science*, 32(2). [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1214/16-sts598> [Accessed on November, 2, 2022]

Frag, S., Schwanen, T., & Dijst, M. (2005, January). Empirical Investigation of Online Searching and Buying and Their Relationship to Shopping Trips. *Transportation Research Record: Journal of the Transportation Research Board*, 1926(1), 242–251. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0361198105192600128> [Accessed on October, 7, 2022]

Farahani, M. G., Shababi, H., & Ashtiani, P. G. (2021, December 26). THE EFFECT OF VISUAL AND FUNCTIONAL CRITERIA OF PACKAGING: CONSUMER EXPECTATIONS OF ELEMENTS FOR DAIRY PRODUCT PACKAGING. *ASEAN Marketing Journal*, 13(2). [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.21002/amj.v13i2.13545> [Accessed on October, 19, 2022]

Foddy, W., & Foddy, W. H. (1993). *Constructing questions for interviews and questionnaires: Theory and practice in social research*. Cambridge university press.

Generation Z - Affiliate Marketing Product Review Site. (2021). [Online] Available from: <https://incomeresult.com/generation-z/> [Accessed on September, 12, 2022]

Gehrt, K. C., Rajan, M. N., Shainesh, G., Czerwinski, D., & O'Brien, M. (2012, August 31). Emergence of online shopping in India: shopping orientation segments. *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, 40(10), 742–758. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1108/09590551211263164> [Accessed on October, 4, 2022]

Haque, S., & Alam, A. (2021). The Role of IT in Transforming the Retail Sector: A Review of Top eCommerce Companies during the COVID-19 Lockdown. *Journal of Applied Computing*, 6(1), 8. [Online] Available from: [http://www.zspublishers.com/jac/download/jac6\(1\)_2.pdf](http://www.zspublishers.com/jac/download/jac6(1)_2.pdf) [Accessed on August 11, 2022]

History.com Editors. (2022, July 14). *Amazon opens for business*. HISTORY. [Online] Available from: <https://www.history.com/this-day-in-history/amazon-opens-for-business> [Accessed on August 16, 2022]

Hoyer, W. D., MacInnis, D. J., & Pieters, R. (2017, January 1). *Consumer Behavior* (7th ed.). Cengage Learning.

India Social Media Statistics 2022 | *Most Used Top Platforms*. (2022, August 6). The Global Statistics - The Data Experts | Statistical Data Reports [Online] Available from: [https://www.theglobalstatistics.com/india-social-media-statistics/#:%7E:text=The%20%20most%20popular%20social.Messenger%20\(324.39%20million%20users\)](https://www.theglobalstatistics.com/india-social-media-statistics/#:%7E:text=The%20%20most%20popular%20social.Messenger%20(324.39%20million%20users).). [Accessed August 10, 2022]

Indrasari, M. (2019). *PEMASARAN DAN KEPUASAN PELANGGAN: pemasaran dan kepuasan pelanggan*. Unitomo Press.

Kalof, L., & Dan, A. (2008). *EBOOK: Essentials of Social Research*. McGraw-Hill Education (UK).

Kalmkar, S., Mujawar, A., & Liyakat, D. K. S. (2022). 3D E-Commers using AR. *International Journal of Information Technology and Computer Engineering*, 26, 18–27. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.55529/ijitc.26.18.27> [Accessed November 7, 2022]

King, G., Keohane, R. O., & Verba, S. (2021). *Designing social inquiry: Scientific inference in qualitative research*. Princeton university press.

Kotler, P. (2000) *Marketing Management: The Millennium Edition*. Person Prentice Hall, Upper Saddle River.

Krosnick, J. A., & Fabrigar, L. R. (1997). Designing Rating Scales for Effective Measurement in Surveys. *Survey Measurement and Process Quality*, 141–164. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118490013.ch6> [Accessed on September, 29, 2022]

Kurian, A. (2018). A STUDY ON THE CUSTOMER SATISFACTION TOWARDS ONLINESHOPPING IN DARJEELING DT WEST BENGAL. *GOSPODARKA I INNOWACJE*, 3. [Online] Available from: <http://www.gospodarkainnowacje.pl/index.php/poland/article/view/13/13> [Accessed on August, 31, 2022]

Kumar, S., & Sadarangani, P. (2018, November 22). An Empirical Study on Shopping Motivation among Generation Y Indian. *Global Business Review*, 22(2), 500–516. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0972150918807085> [Accessed on September, 29, 2022]

Kurniawan, A. R. (2018). *Dasar-Dasar Marketing: Segala Hal Tentang Marketing dan Sales*. Anak Hebat Indonesia.

Lamb, K. (2019, February 18). *Philippines tops world internet usage index with an average 10 hours a day*. The Guardian. [Online] Available from: <https://www.theguardian.com/technology/2019/feb/01/world-internet-usage-index-philippines-10-hours-a-day> [Accessed on September, 25, 2022]

Lumpkin, J. R., & Hite, R. E. (1988, June). Retailers' offerings and elderly consumers' needs: Do retailers understand the elderly? *Journal of Business Research*, 16(4), 313–326. [Online] Available from: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0148-2963\(88\)90064-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0148-2963(88)90064-1) [Accessed on September, 27, 2022]

Luce, R., & Tukey, J. W. (1964). Simultaneous conjoint measurement: A new type of fundamental measurement. *Journal of Mathematical Psychology*, 1(1), 1–27. [Online] Available from: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-2496\(64\)90015-x](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-2496(64)90015-x) [Accessed on November, 4, 2022]

Lukach, B., & Kostiuk, Y. (2022). Current trends in e-marketing—empirical analysis of selected social platform. *Littera Scripta*, 56.

Loureiro, S. M. C., & Breazeale, M. (2016, February 21). Pressing the Buy Button. *Clothing and Textiles Research Journal*, 34(3), 163–178. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0887302x16633530> [Accessed on September, 28, 2022]

Lohr, S. L. (2021). *Sampling: Design and Analysis (Chapman & Hall/CRC Texts in Statistical Science)* (3rd ed.). Chapman and Hall/CRC.

Mallapragada, G., Chandukala, S. R., & Liu, Q. (2016, March). Exploring the Effects of “What” (Product) and “Where” (Website) Characteristics on Online Shopping Behavior. *Journal of Marketing*, 80(2), 21–38. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1509/jm.15.0138> [Accessed on October, 6, 2022]

Marchel, C., & Owens, S. (2007). Qualitative research in psychology: Could William James get a job? *History of Psychology*, 10(4), 301–324. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1037/1093-4510.10.4.301> [Accessed on October, 30, 2022]

Matthias Schonlau, Arthur van Soest, & Arie Kapteyn. (2007). Are “Webographic” or Attitudinal Questions Useful for Adjusting Estimates from Web Surveys Using Propensity Scoring? *Survey Research Methods*, 1(3), 155–163. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.18148/srm/2007.v1i3.70> [Accessed on November, 2, 2022]

Malapane, T. A., & Ndlovu, N. K. (2022). The Adoption of Artificial Intelligence in the South African E-Commerce Space: A Systematic Review. *2022 Systems and Information Engineering Design Symposium (SIEDS)*. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1109/sieds55548.2022.9799403> [Accessed on November, 7, 2022]

Meisya Nazelina, Dewiana Novitasari, Muhamad Agung Ali Fikri, & Masduki Asbari. (2020). THE EFFECT OF BRAND IMAGE, PRICE AND SERVICE QUALITY ON CONSUMER DECISIONS USING DELIVERY SERVICES. *Journal of Industrial Engineering & Management Research*, 1(3), 135–147. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.7777/jiemar.v1i3.74> [Accessed on November, 3, 2022]

M. H. Mostaani, "The Management of Consumer Cooperatives," Paygan Publications, Tehran, 2005. - References - Scientific Research Publishing. (n.d.). [Online] Available from: [https://www.scirp.org/\(S\(351jmbntvnsjt1aadkozje\)\)/reference/referencespapers.aspx?referenceid=607735](https://www.scirp.org/(S(351jmbntvnsjt1aadkozje))/reference/referencespapers.aspx?referenceid=607735) [Accessed on September, 22, 2022]

Mitra, A. (2013). E-commerce in India-A Review. *International journal of marketing, financial services & management research*, 2(2), 126-132.

Millwood, A. (2021, July 22). *Understanding the Consumer Decision Making Process*. Yotpo. [Online] Available from: <https://www.yotpo.com/resources/consumer-decision-making-process-ugc/> [Accessed on September, 21, 2022]

Mitra, A. (2013). E-commerce in India-A Review. *International journal of marketing, financial services & management research*, 2(2), 126-132.

Mirabi, D.V. (2015). A Study of Factors Affecting on Customers Purchase Intention Case Study : the Agencies of Bono Brand Tile in Tehran. [Online] Available from: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/A-Study-of-Factors-Affecting-on-Customers-Purchase-Mirabi/4518676346f0734f26d3915cd612f0e44f889df5> [Accessed on September, 21, 2022]

M, R., & B, V. (2019). DIGITAL MARKETING AND ITS EFFECT ON ONLINE CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOR. *Journal of Services Research*, 19(2), 61–62. [Online] Available from: <https://www.proquest.com/openview/1ddaca83c98223d671e3cb1e12c472ed/1?cbl=28391&pg-origsite=gscholar> [Accessed on July 25, 2022]

O'Boyle, E. J., & Dawson, L. E. (1992). The American Marketing Association code of ethics: instructions for marketers. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 11(12), 921-932.

Omar, A. (2016, April 23). *Sample size estimation and sampling techniques for selecting a representative sample*. [Online] Available from:

https://www.academia.edu/24683129/Sample_size_estimation_and_sampling_techniques_for_selecting_a_representative_sample [Accessed on November, 2, 2022]

Orehek, E., Human, L. J., Sayette, M. A., Dimoff, J. D., Winograd, R. P., & Sher, K. J. (2019). Self-Expression While Drinking Alcohol: Alcohol Influences Personality Expression During First Impressions. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 46(1), 109–123. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0146167219843933> [Accessed on November, 2, 2022]

Park, E. J., & Chung, M. S. (2013). The effects of sociocultural influences of appearance on body dissatisfaction and appearance enhancement behavior of female college students. *The Research Journal of the Costume Culture*, 21(3), 361–375. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.7741/rjcc.2013.21.3.361> [Accessed on November, 3, 2022]

Prasetyo, L., Susanto, P., Sulaiman, F., Supriyanto, S., & Hutabarat, F. A. M. (2022). The Effect of Brand Image On Consumer Purchase Decisions on Products Yamaha (Case Study on PT. Alfa Scorpii Faithful Budi). *Proceedings of the 1st Adpebi International Conference on Management, Education, Social Science, Economics and Technology (AICMEST), Jakarta, 1*. [Online] Available from: <https://series.adpebi.com/index.php/AICMEST/article/download/136/86> [Accessed on November, 3, 2022]

Polit, D. F., & Beck, C. T. (2008). *Nursing research: Generating and assessing evidence for nursing practice*. Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.

Reibstein, D. J. (2002, October 1). What Attracts Customers to Online Stores, and What Keeps Them Coming Back? *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 30(4), 465–473. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1177/009207002236918> [Accessed on October, 4, 2022]

R. Vijayasarathy, Joseph M. Jones, L. (2000, January 1). Intentions to Shop Using Internet Catalogues: Exploring the Effects of Product Types, Shopping Orientations, and Attitudes towards Computers. *Electronic Markets*, 10(1), 29–38. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10196780050033953> [Accessed on September, 29, 2022]

Salomon, I., & Koppelman, F. (1988, July). A framework for studying teleshopping versus store shopping. *Transportation Research Part A: General*, 22(4), 247–255. [Online] Available from: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0191-2607\(88\)90003-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0191-2607(88)90003-9) [Accessed on October,6, 2022]

Scarpi, D., Pizzi, G., & Visentin, M. (2014, May). Shopping for fun or shopping to buy: Is it different online and offline? *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 21(3), 258–267. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2014.02.007> [Accessed on October,7, 2022]

Schmid, B., & Axhausen, K. W. (2019, June). In-store or online shopping of search and experience goods: A hybrid choice approach. *Journal of Choice Modelling*, 31, 156–180.

[Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jocm.2018.03.001> [Accessed on October,7, 2022]

Shah Alam, S., & Mohd Yasin, N. (2010). What factors influence online brand trust: evidence from online tickets buyers in Malaysia. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Electronic Commerce Research*, 5(3). <https://doi.org/10.4067/s0718-18762010000300008> [Accessed on October,4, 2022]

Shorten, A., & Moorley, C. (2014). Selecting the sample. *Evidence Based Nursing*, 17(2), 32–33. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1136/eb-2014-101747> [Accessed on November,2, 2022]

Shim, S., & Kotsiopoulos, A. (1993, September). A Typology of Apparel Shopping Orientation Segments Among Female Consumers. *Clothing and Textiles Research Journal*, 12(1), 73–85. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0887302x9301200110> [Accessed on September, 28, 2022]

Silverman, S. N. (1995, May 1). *An Historical Review and Modern Assessment of the Marketing Mix Concept | Proceedings of the Conference on Historical Analysis and Research in Marketing*. [Online] Available from: <https://ojs.library.carleton.ca/index.php/pcharm/article/view/1867> [Accessed on September, 21, 2022]

Sinha, P. K. (2003, April). Shopping Orientation in the Evolving Indian Market. *Vikalpa: The Journal for Decision Makers*, 28(2), 13–22. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0256090920030202> [Accessed on September, 28, 2022]

Sladek, S., & Grabinger, A. (2014). Gen Z. *Introducing the first Generation of the 21st Century* [Online] Available from: https://www.xyzuniversity.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/08/GenZ_Final-dl1.pdf [Accessed on September, 24, 2022]

Srinivasan, R., & Lohith, C. P. (2017). Pilot Study—Assessment of Validity and Reliability. *India Studies in Business and Economics*, 43–49. [Online] Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-10-3590-6_6 [Accessed on November, 5, 2022]

Statista. (2022, April 30). *India: Top 10 online stores*. [Online] Available from: <https://www.statista.com/forecasts/1218264/india-top-online-stores-india-ecommerce#:%7E:txt=Amazon.in%20is%20leading%20the,revenues%20of%20US%24%20929%20million>. [Accessed on July 29, 2022]

Statistics Solutions. (2021, August 3). *Data Levels of Measurement*. [Online] Available from: <https://www.statisticssolutions.com/dissertation-resources/descriptive-statistics/data-levels-of-measurement/> [Accessed on November,3, 2022]

Sudha, M., & Sheena, K. , (2017, September). Impact of Influencers in Consumer Decision Process: the Fashion Industry. *SCMS Journal of Indian Management*. [Online] Available from: <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/1469/eccb29f76b24e85cba8b6b60adf5ab4932d8.pdf> [Accessed on September, 29, 2022]

Tauber, E. M. (1972, October). Why Do People Shop? *Journal of Marketing*, 36(4), 46. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.2307/1250426> [Accessed on October,7, 2022]

Thangavel, P., Pathak, P., & Chandra, B. (2019, November 7). Consumer Decision-making Style of Gen Z: A Generational Cohort Analysis. *Global Business Review*, 23(3), 710–728. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0972150919880128> [Accessed on September, 27, 2022]

Tourangeau, R., & Rasinski, K. A. (1988). Cognitive processes underlying context effects in attitude measurement. *Psychological Bulletin*, 103(3), 299–314. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.103.3.299> [Accessed on November,2, 2022]

Trochim, W. M., & Donnelly, J. P. (2001). *Research methods knowledge base* (Vol. 2). Macmillan Publishing Company, New York: Atomic Dog Pub..

Tyrer, S., & Heyman, B. (2016). Sampling in epidemiological research: issues, hazards and pitfalls. *BJPsych Bulletin*, 40(2), 57–60.[Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1192/pb.bp.114.050203> [Accessed on November,2, 2022]

Usman, O., & Permatasari, F. F. (2019). The Influences of Advertising Endorser, Brand Image, Brand Equity, Price Promotion, on Purchase Intention. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3510810> [Accessed on October,15, 2022]

Van den Bergh, J., & Pallini, K. (2018, May). Marketing to Generation Z. *Research World*, 2018(70), 18–23.[Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1002/rwm3.20660> [Accessed on September, 29, 2022]

Valliant, R. (2019). Comparing Alternatives for Estimation from Nonprobability Samples. *Journal of Survey Statistics and Methodology*, 8(2), 231–263.[Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1093/jssam/smz003> [Accessed on November, 2, 2022]

Vedatya Institute. (2019). IGITAL MARKETING AND ITS EFFECT ON ONLINE CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOR. *Journal of Services Research*, 19(2). [Online] Available from: <https://www.proquest.com/openview/1ddaca83c98223d671e3cb1e12c472ed/1?cbl=28391&pg-origsite=gscholar> [Accessed on August, 29, 2022]

View of SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING AND CUSTOMER ENGAGEMENT. (n.d.). [Online] Available from: <https://archives.palarch.nl/index.php/jae/article/view/7367/6987> [Accessed on October, 1, 2022]

Walley, K., Custance, P., Taylor, S., Lindgreen, A., & Hingley, M. (2007). The importance of brand in the industrial purchase decision: a case study of the UK tractor market. *Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing*, 22(6), 383–393. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1108/08858620710780145> [Accessed on November, 4, 2022]

What is Purchase Decision | IGI Global. (n.d.). [Online] Available from: <https://www.igi-global.com/dictionary/a-neuromarketing-perspective-for-assessing-the-role-and-impact-of-typefaces-on-consumer-purchase-decision/86606> [Accessed on September, 21, 2022]

Williams, M., Wiggins, R., & Vogt, P. R. (2021). *Beginning Quantitative Research*. SAGE Publications.

Xi, W., Hinton, A., Lu, B., Krotki, K., Keller-Hamilton, B., Ferketich, A., & Sukasih, A. (2022). Analysis of combined probability and nonprobability samples: a simulation evaluation and application to a teen smoking behavior survey. *Communications in Statistics - Simulation and Computation*, 1–17. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1080/03610918.2022.2102181> [Accessed on November, 1, 2022]

Xuan, W., Williams, K., & Peat, J.K. (2001). *Health Science Research: A handbook of quantitative methods* (1st ed.). Routledge.[Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003115922> [Accessed on November, 5, 2022]

Yang, S. (2022). Research on Dynamic Modeling Algorithm of College Students' Learning Motivation Factors based on SPSS and Artificial Intelligence Testing Machine. *2022 International Conference on Inventive Computation Technologies (ICICT)*. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1109/icict54344.2022.9850569> [Accessed on November, 1, 2022]

Yamane, T. (1973) *Statistics: An Introductory Analysis*. 3rd Edition, Harper and Row, New York.
Yamashita, T. (2022). Analyzing Likert scale surveys with Rasch models. *Research Methods in Applied Linguistics*, 1(3), 100022. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rmal.2022.100022> [Accessed on November, 2, 2022]

Zhang, S., & Zhou, L. (2011). The Numbers of Thousand Place of Mersenne Primes. *Applied Mathematics*, 02(11), 1359–1363.[Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.4236/am.2011.211190> [Accessed on October, 30, 2022]

Zimmermann, R., Mora, D., Cirqueira, D., Helfert, M., Bezbradica, M., Werth, D., Weitzl, W. J., Riedl, R., & Auinger, A. (2022). Enhancing brick-and-mortar store shopping experience with an augmented reality shopping assistant application using personalized recommendations and explainable artificial intelligence. *Journal of Research in Interactive Marketing*. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1108/jrim-09-2021-0237> [Accessed on November, 4, 2022]

Appendices

Appendix 1: Dissertation research proposal and ethics form.

UMKDPY-60-M Marketing Dissertation & Research Methods

Dissertation research proposal and ethics form

Name: Pankaj Gurung	Student number: 21069352
UWE email: pankaj2.gurung@live.uwe.ac.uk	Supervisor: Dr. Simon Jones
Project title: Understanding the important factors influencing customers' online purchasing decisions in the fashion clothing for Gen Z consumer of Darjeeling Pulbazar in the district of Darjeeling, West Bengal, India.	
1. Please describe the topic you are interested in, and explain why you think this is a topic worthy of study. Justify your project by producing evidence of the potential usefulness of the research.	
<p>Everything is moving online these days, and the world is becoming more digital. Particularly now that Gen Z is of an age where the internet world is more real than the real one. Online social networking, virtual worlds, and online shopping are all growing in popularity among people, especially since the Covid As stated by (Devi, E. B.) The essential need for digital marketing in everyone's life is created by Covid-19. Customers are willing to invest a significant amount of their free time in researching digital marketing and advertising. Hence, it is a fascinating topic to investigate and comprehend how this generation of consumers think about online shopping, how they choose to purchase goods from online platforms, and how they are gradually moving away from traditional retail in favour of online shopping. With the rise of the Internet, it became significantly simpler for customers to compare prices and options without feeling pressured by sellers, shifting the power equation in their favour. Online retailers' lower transaction costs and benefit both sellers and customers. (Moshrefjavadi et al., 2012)</p>	

2. Does the research project involve any of the following risk factors, tick all that apply:

None

3. What is your main research aim? – consider your research objectives

The purpose of this study is to understand the important factors influencing customers' online purchasing decisions in the fashion clothing for Gen Z consumers.

- Is to understand what factors in the Digital Marketing Mix is more important for Gen Z in online purchasing
- Is to understand the perspective of Gen Z consumers towards online purchasing.
- Is to understand what factors in brand influence in making decisions in online purchasing
- Is to understand whether Gen Z customers prefer to shop online or in-store

4. Provide (700 words Maximum) literature review of key academic theories relevant to your area of study. Consideration needs to be given to establishing the academic foundation for your research and the current academic thinking in the chosen area.

According to (Silverman, 1995) A Marketing Mix the Historical Context and Development of the Marketing Mix, Butler defined marketing in 1911 as "everything the promoter of a product has to accomplish prior to his real use of salesmen and advertising." The agencies of demand formation were thus characterised by Shaw (1916) as "middlemen" (i.e., wholesalers), "direct salesmen," and "advertising." and also defined demand creation organisation as "market analysis" (i.e., market research) and "pricing policies." Converse then precisely described the essential elements of marketing in a corporation in 1930. (product, price, distribution, advertising and selling). As per Cullition (1948), the function of marketing administrator is a "combination of components." Communications, channels, product performance, pricing, and other "order-getting components" have been specified. Borden (1953) applied the term marketing mix to product planning, pricing, branding, distribution channels, personal selling, advertising, promotion, packaging, display, servicing, physical handling, and fact finding) and programme forces (consumer attitudes and methods, competition and government controls.). By 1960, McCarthy had standardised the concept of the marketing mix as the Four P's: Product, Place, Price, and Promotion. Based on the work of Frey (1956) and Kelly and Lazer (1958), "The" marketing mix was created.

- According to (Constantinides, 2014) The term "product" refers to all of the components and aspects required to provide a service that adds value to the customer.
- The price is the amount of money that a customer is willing to pay for a product or service. And according to (Davies & Brush, 1997) Price and other costs of the service sector demonstrate the management of various costs borne by customers in obtaining the benefits from generating the services.
- Place refers to administrative decisions about where customers should receive services, which may include electronic/physical distribution routes (Davies & Brush, 1997)
- Online promotion is addressed to consumers, the impact of the sales campaign can be easily monitored depending on the level of interaction on the website.(Abdul Lasi & Mohamed Salim, 2020

The only component of the marketing mix that a firm can adjust to suit its needs is its product, which also happens to be its biggest source of money. Anjelika, F. . . , & Sinaga, T. M. . . (2022)

Customers' tendency to continuously choose one brand over rivals for goods and services is known as "brand loyalty." Evidence exists to support the idea that brand loyalty is less important to Gen Z customers. Virtually no young customer purchases a product solely based on the brand name due to the ease with which information (reviews, product comparisons, etc.) can now be accessed online.(Thangavel et al., 2019b)

And a purchasing decision is the thinking process that takes a consumer from understanding a need to developing possibilities and selecting a specific brand and product. It is the process through which consumers become aware of and define their wants, get information on how to

best meet these needs, evaluate various available options, make a purchasing decision, and evaluate their purchase. (Millwood, 2021)

5. Produce an initial Conceptual Framework (generated from the literature review) that depicts your potential areas of study. Where applicable show how the theorists reviewed in the literature have contributed to the Conceptual Framework Development.

Conceptual Framework:

6. Outline, explain and justify your choice of research design and methodology

In order to better understand the nature of customers' purchasing behaviour and what influences their decisions to buy any product, particularly on online marketplaces, I will choose for the qualitative research methodology and will use conjoint analysis to determine the factors that affect the decision to buy any product with the help of SPSS. There will be a survey that will be created in Qualtrics. And be distributed among Gen Z users via emails, social media, and internet platforms like Messenger, Whatsapp, Instagram, Telegram, and Line.

7. Based on your current ideas, please outline, explain and justify your choice of data collection method. Show how the data collection tool addresses your research objectives.

For this research, I have chosen the qualitative research method where I will survey 50 respondents who are regular online shoppers in India. In the questionnaire, there will be some general questions such as age group, professional, and some questions regarding purchasing experiences from online platforms. For measurement, the Likert scale will be used. Although the survey will be distributed among 100 - 150 people. The survey will be an online survey. The survey link and QR code will be shared with the participants. Once the data collection will end, all the data will be analysis through SPSS software.

8. Consider what data analysis approaches can be utilised for the data collection method specified.

Qualtrics will use an online survey to gather all the data. The age of the respondents will be at least 18. The outcome will be evaluated using a Likert scale. On a scale of 1 to 7, 1 indicates a strong disagreement, and 7 indicates a strong agreement. If the participant gives a strong agreed response, then most satisfied is taken into consideration, and vice versa. SPSS software will be used to analyse the data.

9. Describe the main steps in your research along with the timescale in which they will be completed bearing in mind your final completion date. You can include a workflow diagram.

This research has a few steps. The first step is to choose a study topic. A literature review, data gathering, data analysis, data interpretation, presentation of the findings, and a conclusion will follow. The majority of the nearly two-month-long study project will be dedicated to gathering and analysing data as well as reviewing relevant literature. The first week will be spent selecting a study topic, and the second will be spent working on the introduction. The last week will be spent focusing on data analysis and interpretation after spending two and a half weeks on the survey and one and a half weeks reviewing the literature. The workflow diagram could look like this:

	GANTT CHART							
WEEK	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Quantitative Research								
Questionnaire								
Survey								
Reporting								
Data Analysis								
Recommendation								

10. If your research is not classed as 'high risk' you still should ensure that you have considered ethical issues, been granted ethical approval by your supervisor, and conducted your research appropriately. Please show evidence / provide details for the following:

Each participant will be made aware of the purpose of the research before agreeing to participate in the survey. Every detail, including how their information will be protected, how their data will be used and secured, and how long data will be used, will be clearly spelled out in a consent form. Within two weeks after the survey date, each participant has the choice to leave the study. My email address will be on the survey form. If a participant emails me to want to be removed from the survey, all of that participant's information will be deleted from the survey and system.

11. Please provide a list of references (using [UWE Harvard format](#)). Those are references you are citing in this proposal.

Devi, E. B. A STUDY ON EFFECT OF COVID-19 ON DIGITAL MARKETING. *COVID 19: Impact and Response Volume VII*, 41

Moshrefjavadi, M. H., Rezaie Dolatabadi, H., Nourbakhsh, M., Poursaeedi, A., & Asadollahi, A. (2012). An Analysis of Factors Affecting on Online Shopping Behavior of Consumers. *International Journal of Marketing Studies*, 4(5). [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijms.v4n5p81> Accessed on October, 28, 2022]

Silverman, S. N. (1995, May 1). *An Historical Review and Modern Assessment of the Marketing Mix Concept | Proceedings of the Conference on Historical Analysis and Research in Marketing*. [Online] Available from: <https://ojs.library.carleton.ca/index.php/pcharm/article/view/1867> [Accessed on September, 21, 2022]

Constantinides, E. (2014, April 22). *Constantinides E., 2006, The Marketing Mix Revisited: Towards the 21st Century Marketing, Journal of Marketing Management, vol. 22, nr 3 -4, pp 407 – 438*. [Online] Available from: https://www.academia.edu/219880/Constantinides_E._2006_The_Marketing_Mix_Revisited_Towards_the_21st_Century_Marketing_Journal_of_Marketing_Management_vol._22_nr_3_-4_pp_407_438 [Accessed on September, 29, 2022]

Davies, W., & Brush, K. E. (1997, January). High-tech industry marketing: The elements of a sophisticated global strategy. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 26(1), 1–13. [Online] Available from: [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0019-8501\(96\)00073-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0019-8501(96)00073-9) [Accessed on September, 22, 2022]

Abdul Lasi, M. B., & Mohamed Salim, S. (2020, October 1). THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN E- MARKETING MIX STRATEGY AND INTEGRATED MARKETING COMMUNICATION: A CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK. *International Journal of Engineering Applied Sciences and Technology*, 5(6), 40–48.[Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.33564/ijeast.2020.v05i06.007> [Accessed on August 20, 2022]

Anjelika, F. . . , & Sinaga, T. M. . . (2022). Influence of Marketing MIX 4P (Product, Price, Place, Promotion) On Purchase Decision at PT. Alfa Scorpii Setia Budi Branch Medan . *Jurnal*

Mantik, 5(4), 2239-2246. [Online] Available from:
<https://iocscience.org/ejournal/index.php/mantik/article/view/1966> [Accessed on October 28, 2022]

Thangavel, P., Pathak, P., & Chandra, B. (2019, November 7). Consumer Decision-making Style of Gen Z: A Generational Cohort Analysis. *Global Business Review*, 23(3), 710–728. [Online] Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0972150919880128> [Accessed on September, 27, 2022]

Millwood, A. (2021, July 22). *Understanding the Consumer Decision Making Process*. Yotpo. [Online] Available from: <https://www.yotpo.com/resources/consumer-decision-making-process-ugc/> [Accessed on September, 21, 2022]

Student Signature	Pankaj Gurung <i>Required on proposal submission</i>	Date: 29/10/2022
Supervisor Signature	Dr Simon Jones 	Date: 1/11/22
Please ensure you keep a copy of this document for your files.		

Appendix 2: Pilot Study.

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	12	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	12	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.875	32

Cronbach's Alpha Test (Reliability Test)

Appendix 2: Survey Questionnaires

Dear Respondent,

You are invited to participate in a survey on "how online purchasing behaviour and what factors in the Digital Marketing Mix have impacted the Gen Z consumer in particular. And how they are shifting from conventional in-store purchases to online purchasing".

My name is Pankaj Gurung and I am currently pursuing MSc in Marketing Communication at the University of the West of England, Bristol (UWE). As part of my studies, I have chosen to research factors in the Digital Marketing Mix have impacted in Gen Z consumer in particular". I have developed a questionnaire to ascertain the information and would be grateful for your help in completing it. It will take approximately 5 to 10 minutes to complete the questionnaire.

It is important for me to understand your viewpoints. Your involvement in this study is entirely voluntary. This project has no foreseeable significant risks. You can leave the survey at any time

I consent to participate in this survey

Yes

No

Are you above 18 years old?

Yes

No

The questions in this block will help the researcher understand how a product influences a consumer's purchase decision.

The respondent must select the best response from the available options.

How often do you buy products (fashion apparel) or services on an e-commerce platform?

More than 5 times a month

3 - 4 times a month

1 - 2 times a month

1 time a month

Never

What factors should be thought about when making an online purchase?

	Strongly agree	Somewhat agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat disagree	Strongly disagree
The design of an app affects the user experience.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The ease of use of an app	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
How its products (clothes) are displayed	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Product availability has a significant effect	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Product genuity, or if a product is exactly what it appears to be	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

The questions in this block will assist the researcher in comprehending how a consumer's decision to buy is influenced by a product's price.

The respondent must select the best response from the available options.

What concerns more to you when making an online purchase?

	Strongly agree	Somewhat agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat disagree	Strongly disagree
Price of a product (clothes) is more important than its quality.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Quality of a product is more important than its price.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Which form of delivery do you prefer the most?

	Strongly agree	Somewhat agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat disagree	Strongly disagree
Cash on delivery	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Online payment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Free return policy	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Free tracking	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Security	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

The questions in this block will aid the researcher in comprehending how a consumer's choice of location affects their purchase.

The respondent must select the best response from the available options.

Which shopping method do you like using the most?

	Strongly agree	Somewhat agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat disagree	Strongly disagree
Online shopping	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
In-store shopping	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Which online platform do you use most frequently to shop (fashion apparel) online?

Amazon India

Meesho

Myntra

Ajio

Other (please specify)

The questions in this block will help the researcher in understanding how customer purchasing decisions are influenced by promotions.

The respondent must select the best response from the available options.

Social media influence (Instagram influencers promoting products)

- Strongly agree
- Somewhat agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Somewhat disagree
- Strongly disagree

What factor of promotions has a significant impact on consumers' purchasing decisions?

	Strongly agree	Somewhat agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat disagree	Strongly disagree
Flash Sales	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Promotional coupons	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Buy 1 Get 1 Free	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Loyalty Points	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

The researcher will gain an understanding of how a branding affects a consumer's buying decision by answering the questions in this block.

The respondent must select the best response from the available options.

When making an online purchase, what brand do you consider the most?

H&M

Zara

Forever 21

Mango

Other (please specify)

What brand characteristics should be considered when shopping online?

	Strongly agree	Somewhat agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat disagree	Strongly disagree
Brand loyalty	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Brand image	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other customers' reviews	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

How important does a brand's recognition affect your trust in online shopping?

	Strongly agree	Somewhat agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat disagree	Strongly disagree
The brand is well known	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The brand is the industry's biggest seller online	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The brand has a high volume of sales online	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Personal Demographic

The respondent must select the best response from the available options.

What gender do you identify with?

Male

Female

Non-binary / third gender

Prefer not to say

How much do you earn each month in salary?

Less than 15,000 INR

15,000 - 25,000 INR

25,000 - 35,000 INR

35,000 - 45,000 INR

Prefer not to say

What is your employment status?

Student

Employed

Unemployed

Other (please specify)

Education (highest degree completed)

- 12th Grade or less
- Graduated High School or equivalent
- Bachelor's degree
- Post-graduate degree

Survey Completion
0% ————— 100%

We thank you for your time spent taking this survey.
Your response has been recorded.